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Abstract	<p>This deliverable summarises progress at month 18 of the AD4GD project on three pilot studies on air quality, water and biodiversity, and identifies the key next steps for all partners to support the implementation. The pilot studies are designed to demonstrate the feasibility of re-using, developing, extending and integrating a range of tools, semantics and standards to facilitate data-driven decision making on Green Deal priority topics.</p> <p>The progress described includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • engagement with stakeholders; • requirements gathering; • identification of existing re-usable components, data and services which can support the pilots and, more broadly, the Green Deal Data Space;
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identification of gaps, and of components required to fill those gaps; • progress on development and integration of the identified components. <p>The purpose of Deliverable 6.1 is to review the context and lessons learnt in the first 6 months of the pilot work package, and to identify and plan priority actions for the next 18 months to ensure robust integration of accessible, re-usable tools and workflows by the end of the project. Where deliverables already exist from the project that document underpinning technologies and services, these will be signposted. Evaluation of performance and scaling potential is beyond the scope of the current deliverable, and will be addressed in its second iteration (D6.2). The current deliverable focuses primarily on the integration of existing and bespoke tools to support the workflows necessary to consume, use and produce data and metadata for the three identified pilot case studies.</p> <p>We describe a human-centred co-design approach employed by FIT in eliciting high-level requirements for interfaces and user experience in the Green Deal Data Space, both during the project and in a dedicated workshop in September 2023. This work has required us to work closely with sister projects and existing GEO initiatives to ensure efficiency and interoperability.</p> <p>For each pilot, we describe the initial rationale, indicators to be computed and stakeholders, before delineating the relative contribution (and potential future contribution) of EO, citizen science, socio-economic and IoT data. Next we present the value proposition and design for an end-user tool (to be developed by FIT) which will allow GDDS users to easily access the application or workflow, with a high-level view of the underlying data and processing services. Finally, for each pilot study, we describe the technical components that have been identified as necessary to support such interfaces from end to end, including 12 bespoke tools and components being developed by project partners to ease the integration of existing solutions.</p> <p>Progress on these 12 technical components are explained, including whether each is being re-used, extended or specifically developed within tasks and work packages of the project. In each case, URLs are given for supporting demonstrations, instances or code repositories. We have aligned their development and iteratively integrated them at two face-to-face project hackathons in October 2023 and February 2024. We then revisit each pilot study to assess the progress of integration and development, and identify priorities for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months, aiming towards an integration that can be documented and evaluated within the final 6 months of the project.</p>
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AD4GD	All Data 4 Green Deal
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIM	Agriculture Information Model
API	Application Programming Interface
AQ	Air Quality
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange.
AU	Aston University
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CBM	Community-Based Monitoring
CHE	CO ₂ Human Emissions project
CHH	Copernicus Health Hub
CitSci	Citizen Science
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CoCO ₂	“Prototype system for a Copernicus CO ₂ service” project
COG	Cloud Optimised Geotiff
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
CREAF	Centro De Investigacion Ecologica Y Aplicaciones Forestales
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CSVW	CSV on the Web
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPI	Data Preparation and Integration
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
DTES	The Territory and Sustainability Department of the Catalan Government
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components

EEA	European Environment Agency
EIONet	European Environment Information and Observation Network
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
EV	Essential Variable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FDB	Fields DataBase
FIT	Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology
FIWARE	Future Internet-Ware
FLC	Functional Landscape Connectivity
FTP	File Transfer Protocol (FTP)
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GD	Green Deal
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDIM	Green Deal Information Model
GeoDCAT	Geospatial Data Catalog Vocabulary
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GIS	Geographic Information System
GRIB	General Regularly distributed Information in Binary form
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HCD	Human-Centered-Design
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ICT	Index of Terrestrial Connectivity
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
IoT	Internet of Things
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
JRC	Joint Research Centre
JRE	Java Runtime Environment
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
KBA	Key Biodiversity Area

KWB	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin
LCS	Low-Cost Sensor
LULC	Land-Use/Land-Cover
LZW	Lempel–Ziv–Welch
ML	Machine Learning
MPI	Message Passing Interface
MUCSC	The Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces for Linked Data
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide
O ₃	Ozone
PM ₁₀	Particulate Matter with sizes less than 10 micrometres
PM _{2.5}	Particulate Matter with sizes less than 2.5 micrometres
PSNC	Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SAFE	Sentinel-1 SAFE XML Product
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDI	Serial digital interface
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide
SOSA	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator
SOSA/SSN	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator/Semantic Sensor Network
STA	Sensor Things API
STApplus	Sensor Things API plus (extension of STA)
TAPIS	Tables from APIs for Sensors
THREDDS	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
VERIFY	"Verifying greenhouse gas emissions" project
WAI	Water Availability Index
WCMC	World Conservation Monitoring Centre
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WHO	World Health Organization

WMO	World Meteorological Organization
WMS	Web Map Service
WP	Work Package
WQI	Water Quality Index
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable summarises pilot study progress at month 18 of the AD4GD project, and identifies the key next steps for all partners to support the implementation of the three pilot studies. The pilot studies are designed to demonstrate the feasibility of re-using, developing, extending and integrating a range of tools, semantics and standards to facilitate data-driven decision making on Green Deal priority topics.

Progress described includes: engagement with stakeholders; requirements gathering; identification of existing re-usable components, data and services which can support the pilots and, more broadly, the Green Deal Data Space; identification of gaps, and of components required to fill those gaps; and progress on development of the identified components.

1 INTRODUCTION - PURPOSE & SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of the deliverable is to review the context and lessons learnt in the first 6 months of the pilot work package, and to identify and plan priority actions for the next 18 months to ensure robust integration of accessible, re-usable tools and workflows by the end of the project. Where deliverables already exist from the project that document underpinning technologies and services, these will be signposted. Evaluation of performance and scaling potential is beyond the scope of the current deliverable, and will be addressed in its second iteration (D6.2). The current deliverable focuses primarily on the integration of existing and bespoke tools to support the workflows necessary to consume, use and produce data and metadata for the three identified pilot case studies.

Section 2.1 sets the general context for the pilots, and situates them within the Green Deal Data Space, highlighting the particular challenges that each one exemplifies. This section includes a mapping of pilot elements to a conceptual diagram of the Green Deal Data Space. We then (Section 2.2) describe the human-centred co-design approach employed by FIT in eliciting high-level requirements for interfaces and user experience in the Green Deal Data Space, both during the project and in a dedicated workshop in September 2023). This work has required us to work closely with sister projects such as B3 and FAIR-i-CUBE and with existing GEO initiatives to ensure efficiency and interoperability.

Sections 3, 4, 5 detail the water pollution, biodiversity and air quality pilot studies respectively. For each, we describe the initial rationale, indicators to be computed and stakeholders, before delineating the relative contribution (and potential future contribution) of EO, citizen science (hereafter referred to as CitSci), socio-economic and IoT data. Next we present the value proposition and design for an end-user tool (to be developed by FIT) which will allow GDDS users to easily access the application or workflow, with a high-level view of the underlying data and processing services. Finally, for each pilot study, we describe the technical components that have been identified as necessary to support such interfaces from end to end, including bespoke tools and components being developed by project partners to ease the integration of existing solutions.

Section 6 describes in more detail these technical components, describing whether each is being re-used, extended or specifically developed within the project, and details progress on their development or evaluation. Many of these technical components are deliverables from other project work packages, and this has allowed us to align their development and iteratively integrate them at two hackathons in October 2023 and February 2024. Where these components are described in existing deliverables, this is signposted to avoid redundancy. In each case, URLs are given for supporting demonstrations, instances or code repositories. In Section 7, we revisit each pilot study to assess the progress of integration and development, and identify priorities for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months, aiming towards an integration that can be documented and evaluated within the final 6 months of the project (in the form of D6.2).

Section 8 is a complete list of references, followed by appendices giving more detail on those pilot research and technical investigations which are not fully described in other deliverables.

2 CONTEXT OF THE PILOTS

2.1 POSITIONING WITHIN THE GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE

The pilot studies selected cover key challenges relating to Green Deal priorities, each requiring the transparent and principled use of data and services from multiple sources to support and defend strategic decisions. To set the technical context of the Green Deal Data Space, Figure 1 shows our extension of a proposal from our sister project USAGE proposal for evolution of the original Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) building blocks as a consequence of a mapping to current standards. The original diagram can be seen in USAGE D3.2 <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1FyvNkWkAWkuKKHh-3l529VUu5LlKyU5E/view>. This version has been adapted by consensus based on AD4GD consortium experience and insights from the development of the pilots.

AD4GD

Figure 1: Schematic of elements required to support the delivery of the Green Deal Data Space (adapted from deliverable 3.2 of USAGE project- Grant Agreement no 101059950).

The figures below show each pilot study as it can be framed with reference to these building blocks. Successful delivery of the pilots relies on a range of underpinning standards, tools and technical protocols, which are identified in Figure 2, Figure 3 and Figure 4. A number of components are shared between the pilots and all will be developed or extended in a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and modular fashion, enabling re-use beyond the AD4GD project for a sustainable Green Deal Data Space.

These reference diagrams are very complete, and are broken down into more specific detail in Sections 3, 4, 5 and 7. Sections 3.8, 4.9, and 5.9 break down the components needed to deliver the pilots as planned. Technical developments which fill identified gaps are described in Section 6, and progress on each pilot pipeline is reviewed and illustrated in Section 7.

For each pilot, a community of practice is being identified and consulted in order to verify the value and relevance of the proposed outcomes. The pilots and their stakeholders are explained in more detail in Sections 3, 4, and 5.

Pilot 1: Water Quality

AD4GD

Figure 2: Water pilot.

Pilot 1 is led by KWB, and relates to a range of ecosystem services provided by urban lakes, including recreation. We specifically focus on water availability and quality in urban lakes in Berlin. In this pilot, satellite data and volunteered CitSci measurements have the potential to enrich a data space which is currently dominated by IoT sources such as *in situ* sensors for water level, conductivity, oxygen etc. The available *in situ* data is sparse, especially for smaller lakes and these additional data sources will allow project partners to build prediction models based on machine learning which allow stakeholders to monitor and predict the state and trend of lakes in terms of their water availability and quality. A Water Quality Index (WQI) and a Water Availability Index (WAI) for monitoring and visualisation will be developed and validated as part of this pilot, in partnership between KWB, AU and ATOS.

Pilot 2: Biodiversity

Figure 3: Biodiversity pilot.

Pilot 2: (Biodiversity) will establish key locations for landscape functional connectivity and endangered species persistence by explicitly combining and cross-validating the results from different accepted modelling approaches, based on time series of land-use / land-cover (LULC) maps. While satellite data and human observations from CitSci are established tools for mapping and monitoring species distributions and landscapes, IoT technologies can also contribute to monitor threats and verify their impacts on endangered species. The data pre-processing and computational methods for connectivity calculation can be complex to replicate and thus, in addition to a user client for accessing the workflow, this pilot will deploy modular analysis components which can be deployed on a range of platforms. This pilot is led by AU and CREA in partnership.

Pilot 3: Air Quality

AD4GD

Figure 4: Air pollution pilot.

Pilot 3 (Air quality and pollution) is a context where the use of Earth Observation (EO) data is well-established by the pilot leads (ECMWF) to generate authoritative air quality maps and forecasts at a global scale (e.g. 10 - 40 km resolution). IoT data and CitSci observations offer the potential to enrich these products and enable further insights into the air pollution on a city scale. This is particularly relevant in the context of health monitoring in the short-term (e.g. early warning systems) as well as long-term (e.g. an improved data base for medical studies). However, these new observations from low-cost sensors must be integrated and systematically quality-checked in order to identify bias and error, and to ensure a scientifically robust result. The pilot will make first scientific assessments of the feasibility of this integration of IoT data into the forecasting and can also enrich the practice of citizen scientists by contributing assessments of instrument and measurement quality for open analysis and discussion.

2.2 HUMAN-CENTRED METHODOLOGY AND CO-DESIGN

In order to build meaningful digital solutions within the AD4GD project, the methodological approach of FIT is based on the Human-Centered-Design (HCD) methodology, complemented by Co-Design methods.

Human-Centered Design (HCD) is a methodology used for designing, evaluating and implementing interactive computing systems for human use (Churchill, Bowser, and Preece, 2013). Its key elements are

user-centered iterative design and prototyping. The HCD reflects the need to understand the context of use of a computing system and its key users and their tasks and needs. The name ‘iterative design’ reflects the fact that feedback from users and stakeholders is repeatedly collected and integrated into the systems, and prototyping reflects the important role of tangible artifacts in this feedback process (Gould and Lewis, 1985). The *ISO-standard Ergonomics of human system interaction - Part 210: Human-centered design for interactive systems 9241-210* thus lays the basis for our approach (ISO, 2010).

We additionally apply **Co-Design** (or participatory design) methods to ensure ongoing user and stakeholder involvement throughout the whole system design and development process (Steen, 2013). Co-design strengthens the understanding of user needs and behaviours by actively engaging a diverse group of stakeholders, fostering collaboration and ensuring that the design process benefits from diverse perspectives and experiences, and as such complementing the HCD process to create usable solutions and services (Muller and Kuhn, 1993; Sanders, 2002).

Figure 5 illustrates the human-centered workflow applied in the AD4GD project.

Human-Centered Workflow AD4GD project

Figure 5: AD4GD human-centred workflow.

During the AD4GD project kick-off meeting held in September 2022 in Barcelona, Spain, a **Preparatory Stakeholder Analysis** workshop was held to identify and prioritise potential stakeholders and users of systems and services to be developed by the AD4GD project.

The highest priority stakeholders were interviewed and the results were discussed and reflected upon with each respective pilot partner in the **Remote Pilot Preparation Workshops**. As a result of these workshops, a first set of user requirements was defined and documented in Deliverable 1.1.

The **Pilot Kick-Off Workshop** was held between 11th and 14th of September 2023 in Bonn, Germany. The aim was to engage the pilot partners in co-creation of the first prototype designs of the user interfaces for the tools to be developed within each pilot. The results of this workshop are summarised in this deliverable as follows: for Pilot 1 in the Sections 3.4 and 3.6; for Pilot 2 in 4.3 and 4.7; and for Pilot 3 in 5.7.

The paper prototypes resulting from the Pilot-Kickoff Workshop were developed into simple clickable wireframes. As part of **iterative evaluation**, the wireframes were reviewed by the pilot partners and, based on their feedback, Version 2 of the prototypes were generated. Interviews and usability tests will be carried out with appropriate user groups to generate further updated versions of the user interfaces.

Using the HCD and co-design approaches, user interfaces will be developed from low to high fidelity and iteratively tested to deliver tools that are usable for the defined user groups.

2.3 TECHNICAL COMPONENT DEVELOPMENT

A face-to-face AD4GD project hackathon was held between 24th and 27th of October 2024 at Aston University, Birmingham, UK. The aim of the hackathon was to start the development of technical components based on a set of requirements identified and refined in online meetings before the hackathon.

The hackathon was focused around 4 main areas of development: dataspace connectors, connectivity workflow, semantic enrichment, and injection of sensor data into STA/STApplus. A set of requirements for each was identified before the hackathon. These requirements are publicly accessible on GitHub: <https://github.com/AD4GD/requirements>.

The initial requirements have evolved through subsequent development iterations coordinated remotely between the partners, leading to the identification of a set of 12 components / component groups needed to support the pilots and the GGDS. These 12 technical elements formed the focus for a second face-to-face project hackathon in February 2024 in Torino, Italy – they are described in Section 6, and are mapped to the pilots in Sections 3, 4, and 5.

3 PILOT 1 – WATER POLLUTION

3.1 INITIAL PILOT RATIONALE AND DESIGN

Berlin's ecosystems face challenges related to the city's rapid densification (300.000 new inhabitants in the last 10 years) and climate change. 30% of the total area of Berlin is covered by forests and other green and open space and 6% is covered by water. The latter comprises not only the Spree-Havel river and lake system, but also more than 300 small urban lakes. Many of those small urban lakes suffer from the increased occurrence of temperature and rain extremes. At the same time, they have great potential for biodiversity and provide important recreational areas for inhabitants. In addition, small lakes <50 ha are not part of the monitoring and action cycles of the EU Water Framework Directive, and accordingly only receive higher attention in individual cases (e.g. where they function as bathing waters).

Today, no simple methods are known to identify particularly polluted lakes, to investigate the type of pollution and to prioritise and evaluate measures. Accordingly, solutions driven by combining available data and deploying AI technologies offer great potential to improve the management of small urban lakes, identify drivers and indicators for stressors of water quality and make better informed decisions.

Therefore pilot 1 aims to develop a condition index (WQI or water quality index) for polluted small urban lakes by combining IoT, CitSci and EO data with AI technologies to identify drivers and indicators for stressors of water quality. A Water Availability Index (WAI) will also be developed by combining EO data with IoT and CitSci assessments of water level. The pilot is led by KWB.

3.2 INDICATORS AND METRICS

The overall objective is the prioritisation and derivation of measures for small lakes in Berlin. For this purpose, it should be possible to compare the lakes with each other and to describe the development of a lake in as automated a way as possible. Four key indicators are the basis of the overall assessment, and these arise from the measurement of either status or trend in water quality or water availability.

3.2.1 WATER QUALITY STATUS

Good water quality in a lake can be limited by elevated concentrations of nutrients or pollutants. High nutrient concentrations lead to increased growth of phytoplankton and turbidity of the water, and increase the likelihood of pronounced algal blooms. As the algal biomass decreases, the oxygen content of the sediment and deeper water layers can drop significantly, creating hostile conditions for many organisms.

Although the nutrient content of the lakes also varies naturally, higher nutrient loads are often introduced into the lakes, particularly through urban storm water runoff.

High levels of pollutants, such as biocides or heavy metals, can be toxic to aquatic organisms. The source of pollutants in urban small lakes is primarily storm water runoff from roads or buildings.

3.2.2 WATER QUALITY TREND

Water quality naturally differs between lakes. In urban lakes, the difference may be anthropogenic, but still acceptable. What is most important is the *consistency* of water quality. Trends over several years can be used to better estimate whether, and in which direction, the quality of a lake is changing. If water quality decreases, countermeasures can be taken at an early stage. Additionally, the success of measures can be evaluated by the use of trends.

3.2.3 WATER AVAILABILITY STATUS

Water scarcity affects a number of the key ecosystem services offered by urban lakes, including recreational, provisioning and cooling functions, and is also highly dependent on environmental conditions including precipitation.

3.2.4 WATER AVAILABILITY TREND

The objective is similar to that of the water quality trend. It is likely that water availability is even more seasonally variable and weather dependent than water quality, so robust trends gain even more value over description of a current condition. In addition to the long-term trend of water availability of a lake, the comparison of several small lakes at the same point in time can also support prioritisation, by answering questions such as: 'which lakes will dry out first if there is no rain for a certain period of time?'

3.3 IMPACT OF EXTERNAL FACTORS

- GROUNDWATER

Since Berlin is largely located in a glacial valley, many lakes are influenced by groundwater. However, it is often not clear how strong this groundwater impact is. This information is important in planning measures such as disconnecting (because of too high pollutant or nutrient load) or connecting (because of lack of water availability) urban areas to the lake. In addition, the impact of groundwater may change due to construction activities in the lake watershed.

- STORMWATER RUNOFF

Stormwater runoff from urban areas can contain high concentrations of nutrients and pollutants, and if discharged into small lakes, can cause corresponding problems (see Section 3.2.1). Conversely, stormwater runoff provides a potential source of water to support small lakes with low water availability.

The load of stormwater runoff is strongly related to the type of sealed surfaces from which the stormwater originates. It is possible to estimate the emission to a water body depending on the surrounding urban structure type / urban landuse. This indirect estimation is the only approach that can be used for a prediction of water quality other than direct pollutant measurements.

By looking at current or potential stormwater watersheds, areas with low loads could be preferentially connected to lakes, or areas with high loads could be targeted for disconnection. These two potential measures are two of the most important approaches to improving water quality and water availability in small lakes.

3.4 RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

Based on the project findings to date, the following stakeholder groups were identified in the context of Pilot 1. Their high priority needs are documented in the form of User Stories.

Members of the Berlin Senate are in charge of the long-term strategy for all surface waters. They need summarised and aggregated data, they care more about water trends and they need recommendations for action.

“As a member of the senate, I want to see long-term trends concerning the quality and availability of the water in small lakes, to decide on an overall strategy for the small lakes in Berlin”.

“As a member of the senate, I want to close knowledge gaps, to decide on an holistic overall strategy for the small lakes in Berlin”.

Members of the districts in Berlin are in charge of managing small lakes.

“As a member of a district in Berlin, I want to see the state of lakes in my own district but decide on my district's rules how to spend the available resources to fulfil the overall strategy by implementing specific actions”.

Researchers at KWB and other water research institutes are requested by the Senate or the districts for their expertise and they have to perform studies to support the decision makers.

“As a researcher at KWB, I want to estimate water quality and availability, to enable the development of long-term strategies and prioritization of rehabilitation measures.”

“As a researcher at KWB, I want to easily access standardized data, to save time when searching and processing data and transfer the solution to other regions.”

Citizens benefit from lakes in good condition in different ways. For this reason they want to participate in the development of aquatic ecosystems. With access to scientific data/information they have stronger arguments and are able to put pressure on decision makers / politicians.

“As a citizen of Berlin, I want to provide data and information, to make others (e.g. politicians) aware of grievances.”

“As a citizen of Berlin, I want to participate in the decision-making process to improve the quality of aquatic ecosystems in my city.”

“As a Citizen Scientist in Berlin, I want to "easily" connect different data to get answers to existing questions and to find solutions to identified problems.”

“As a Citizen Scientist in Berlin, I want to inform myself about the lake condition and access governmental data.”

3.5 METHODOLOGIES AND TOOLS

The following section proposes solutions for determining baselines and trends, as well as some possible measures. These solutions make use of different types of data. What they all have in common is that, once established, they can be carried out in a relatively automated fashion, and without much additional effort. Because the solutions use different approaches, they are especially strong when applied in combination, since they complement each other and allow for mutual validation by showing whether statements are ambiguous. For all approaches it is necessary that they are trained and verified by a sufficient number of measurements. Therefore every new measurement program at a small lake in Berlin will contribute to an improvement of the results.

3.5.1 REMOTE SENSING DATA FOR THE ESTIMATION OF WATER QUALITY

- BACKGROUND

Satellites measure the reflected and emitted radiation of specific wavelengths. The proportion of radiation reflected by water at a specific wavelength depends, among other things, on the turbidity or colour of the water. In particular, pigments of phytoplankton, for example chlorophyll, have a large influence on the backscattering of light. It is very difficult to infer absolute turbidity values or chlorophyll concentrations from a few pixels available in small lakes, though in recent experiments a good correlation between annual average reflectance and lake trophic index has been found using just one pixel. However, the method is probably limited to lakes with a surface area significantly larger than this pixel size. If 3000 square metres is taken as a lower limit, 130 lakes in Berlin would be large enough.

- ADVANTAGES FOR BERLIN

ESA's Sentinel-2 program has been measuring multi-spectral surface reflectance for over 5 years, and the Landsat data series history is much longer. Based on a few pixels, the development of water quality over the last 5-10 years of small lakes could be estimated (→ [Water quality trend](#), → [Water quality status \(nutrients\)](#)). Eventually, the method could be optimised to a resolution of up to 10 x 10 m. In the worst case, the resolution would be 60 x 60 m, which would exclude small lakes but include medium-sized lakes.

- TASKS IN BERLIN

The data need to be cross-checked with on-site measurements. Chlorophyll-a and/or turbidity and/or nutrients would need to be measured at as many different lakes as possible over the next 2 years, and ideally the trophic index would need to be determined. For additional training and calibration, measurement data from the last 5 years can be used. These are mainly available for large lakes investigated by the Senate, but there are also a number of special measurement programs, for example in the Berlin districts.

- TASKS IN AD4GD

In many lakes not only one, but several pixels can be used. This allows for the analysis of sensitivity: what is the local variability within a lake? How trustworthy is the statement if only one pixel is available?

So far it is very complicated to download this data. It would be nice to have a possibility

- where you specify the coordinates in the centre of a lake, the algorithm then automatically detects the extent of the lake and downloads all pixels in this polygon with the data,
- alternatively, specifying a polygon from a GIS system and downloading all pixels that lie within the polygon

for all available images within a timeframe. Development and evaluation of such functionality relates mainly to WP4, but a proof-of-concept analysis with SENTINEL data has already been completed and is described in Section 7.1.

3.5.2 REMOTE SENSING DATA FOR THE ESTIMATION OF WATER AVAILABILITY

- BACKGROUND

Similar to the use of satellite data to assess water quality, it is possible to distinguish per pixel whether it is a water pixel or not. For pixels that describe both water and surrounding land, a transition should be recognizable. This makes it possible to estimate the spatial extent of lakes at any point in time.

- ADVANTAGES FOR BERLIN

The spatial extent of lakes can be determined for each satellite image (without clouds). This allows short-term changes (depending on the weather) and also long-term trends to be described (→ [water availability trend](#)).

The condition of the lakes themselves, on the other hand, cannot be estimated in this way, since no water volumes are described. If weather data and groundwater data are included, it may be possible to draw conclusions about the influence of groundwater or stormwater on water availability (→ [Groundwater](#), → [Stormwater](#)).

- TASKS IN BERLIN

The calculated values from remote sensing must be checked for plausibility. For this purpose, water level data are particularly suitable, as they are collected selectively at some lakes or also area-wide in Neukölln. Alternatively, CitSci data (e.g., photos of the same location) could serve as a reference. This would require a methodology for estimating lake extent from such photographs.

- TASKS IN AD4GD

Here, the same selection algorithm can be applied as for the use of satellite data for water quality, however, the "transition pixels" containing water surface and shore area would possibly be used in addition. For each image, the number of pixels describing a lake (and, if applicable, the water portion of the "transition pixels") can be determined. Groundwater data and weather data are used as sensor data for further analysis. Here, IoT work within WP3 is of particular relevance.

3.5.3 CITIZEN SCIENCE AS LAKE MONITORING SUPPORT

- BACKGROUND

There are many small lakes in Berlin but even more people. While the survey of the lakes by experts is very time-consuming and expensive, simple tasks can also be carried out by residents or interested persons, which can lead to valuable insights. This can range from photos taken at a certain position (e.g. water level) to small measurements such as visibility. The target group depends on the complexity of the tasks. For example, photos can be taken by any person passing by, more complicated tasks could be done by participants who may have been trained beforehand or even provided with material.

- ADVANTAGES FOR BERLIN

CitSci allows the monitoring of lakes without high costs (→ [water quality status \(nutrients\)](#), → [water availability status](#)). The quality of the data may be lower compared to expert assessment, but on the other hand, CitSci observations can increase the coverage and timeliness of monitoring data. Since very little is known about the small lakes, even a small but steady amount of information can be very valuable. Trends can be derived through appropriate interpretation of the data, but this first requires a long period of data collection. In addition, people can actively participate in lake maintenance and be made aware of it. This gives the people involved a good feeling and by feeding back the evaluated data, it improves our knowledge of these small bodies of water

- TASKS IN BERLIN

A query needs to be developed that will provide the highest benefit to lake maintenance. What easy-to-grasp information is most valuable for the objectives? Depending on the target group, either information boards need to be installed (e.g. with barcodes or short instructions) so that people can easily participate or interested people need to be trained. The latter could also be done, for example, in public workshops by the KWB in coordination with those responsible in Berlin.

- TASKS IN AD4GD

In order for residents to participate, participation must be made as easy as possible, and ideally should rely on standardised protocols such as query forms. For example, a barcode could open a page on which specific

questions are asked or a photo can be uploaded (ideally in German). For the option with trained participants, it might also be possible to install an app.

The submitted data must then be stored and processed. Since the quality of the data is difficult to verify, the variability (e.g., assessments by different people at the same place / time) of the data must be checked. Different answers could be linked together to get an increased significance or to increase the robustness of observations. It must also be examined how the observations differ in time and space and whether there are particular patterns, meaning that this aspect of water monitoring can benefit from the work of both WP2 (CitSci), WP5 (AI / machine learning) and WP4 (data trustworthiness framework).

3.5.4 *IN SITU* SENSORS - OXYGEN SENSORS FOR ESTIMATING WATER QUALITY

- BACKGROUND

The oxygen content is related to almost all processes in a water body. Therefore, it is practically impossible to infer from a single oxygen measurement what is currently happening in the water body. However, daily fluctuations and seasonal variations can be mapped by long time series. The expression of these fluctuations is strongly influenced by the biological activity in the water body and thus by the water quality in terms of nutrients.

In nutrient-rich/eutrophic lakes, oxygen supersaturation is expected during sunshine due to intensive growth of phytoplankton. Conversely, the intensive growth leads to oxygen depletion above the sediment / in the deep water of the lake.

- ADVANTAGES FOR BERLIN

Oxygen measurements over a long period of time in different lakes can be used to derive fluctuation patterns that allow conclusions to be drawn about the water quality. Since oxygen concentration is a very complex and sensitive parameter, either very long time series are necessary, or other parameters must be taken into account. Where it is possible to distinguish patterns for certain lake conditions solely on the basis of this oxygen curve, lake condition can be determined automatically with oxygen probes (→ [Water quality status \(nutrients\)](#)).

Oxygen content can provide information about the differing states of water bodies, but this concentration is highly dependent on weather and season. Therefore it may be necessary to acquire additional covariate information such as weather data or groundwater levels. If condition is to be compared between lakes, then oxygen should be measured at the same time to ensure the same prevailing environmental conditions (→ [Water quality status \(nutrients\)](#)).

- TASKS IN BERLIN

To find a correlation between oxygen fluctuation patterns and water quality, oxygen probes have to be installed in as many different small lakes in Berlin as possible over a longer period of time. KWB has an opportunity to provide some of these probes (probably 3 to 4). Each probe will be installed in a lake that is already part of another monitoring program, as this will allow us to combine the AD4GD oxygen measurements with other important water quality parameters.

Oxygen measurements will be taken near the surface to obtain information about the daily and seasonal oxygen dynamic depending on the surrounding weather conditions such as sunshine intensity or precipitation. The part of oxygen fluctuation that cannot be explained by the surrounding conditions is expected to contain information on the water quality. A model will be developed based on the accompanying monitoring parameters.

- TASKS IN AD4GD

The oxygen data is made available online with KWB as data provider. It is typical IoT data that needs to be integrated into the Green Deal Data Space. The patterns can be recognized either with methods of classical statistics or with machine learning algorithms. The inclusion of ancillary covariate data available online can also be based on AI methods. This relates mainly to WP3 on IoT data integration, and to WP5 (AI/ML).

3.5.5 SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA - ESTIMATION OF NUTRIENT AND POLLUTANT EMISSIONS

- BACKGROUND

At KWB, the nutrient and pollutant content in stormwater runoff has already been measured in several projects. In the R2Q project, average pollutant concentrations were derived from these measured values as a function of urban land use types or even area-specific use (building, street, yard) and converted to pollutant loads (<https://github.com/KWB-R/r2q>). The loads can be combined with ecotoxicological reference values and water balance parameters such as discharge from the lake or water volume of the lake. If the surrounding infrastructure and the construction of the separate sewer system are known, the calculation can be performed quickly.

- ADVANTAGES FOR BERLIN

Different characteristic values could be calculated for each lake. What material loads can be expected if all surrounding areas are connected? What material loads are to be expected at the current connection rate? Which are the particularly polluted and weakly polluted areas that could be disconnected or connected as a matter of priority? Ultimately, this is important information for balancing the goals of targeted water quality and water availability. But it is also a robust basis for prioritising stormwater runoff treatment such as retention filters. Emission simulation is the only way to indirectly describe the state of water quality with respect to pollutants without directly measuring pollutants (→ *Water quality status (pollutants)*). Once the results of the simulation have been checked for plausibility, various connection scenarios can be used to describe future water quality states (→ *Water quality trend (prediction)*).

- TASKS IN BERLIN

The different data (types) on urban structure, sewers and water bodies have to be brought together. For this purpose, the urban structure data must be divided into classes with which the R2Q tool can be applied.

After prioritisation by pollutant loads, it should be checked for plausibility with *in situ* pollutant and nutrient measurements.

- TASKS IN AD4GD

The evaluation is based on a combination of GIS data and measured data in stormwater runoff. GIS data are available online for many regions, but often in different formats and quality. Across countries, different languages are involved. At the same time, these data are relevant to many Green Deal issues. The goal of a Green Deal Data Space will be to create the best possible linkage here, so that local solutions are more transferable to other areas. This goal will depend particularly on the semantic harmonisation work of WP1.

At the same time, data sets from research projects and special monitoring programs are very important with regard to environmental issues. It would be beneficial if not only continuously collected data but also such research data sets were part of the Green Deal Data Space. One possibility would be the integration of Zenodo, where amongst others a large dataset of KWB on the pollutant content in stormwater runoff is published.

3.6 UPDATED PROBLEM AND SOLUTION STATEMENT

Based on the project findings to date, the following updated Problem and Solution Statements were generated for the Pilot 1 Case.

Updated Problem Statement

Lakes in and around Berlin play a crucial role in local climate, supporting biodiversity, and providing recreational spaces for citizens. Small lakes (in Berlin) are not under the regulation of the European Water Framework Directive and therefore lack adequate monitoring of the water quality. In addition, due to limited resources (e.g. financial or human) bigger lakes are prioritised. Besides water quality, water availability is also important. The two topics are strongly connected to each other, for example stormwater raises the water availability, but has a bad influence on water quality. Furthermore, climate change leads to hotter summers and less water in the lakes and therefore the whole ecosystem in the lakes can die. Decision makers today lack appropriate information to take action to improve the water quality and availability in small lakes.

Updated solution statement (in AD4GD)

First, we need to make water quality and availability of small lakes in Berlin visible and comparable through developing a reliable WQI and WAI. The computation of these metrics should be automated as far as possible due to the limited resources. Second, we need to provide decision making support that communicates these results and indicates which lakes need actions first (due to limited resources we can not take actions at all lakes). The decision making can be supported by the Lake Splashboard tool, that is described in Section 3.7. Transferability of the solution to another region is desirable.

3.7 END-USER TOOL DESCRIPTION

For Pilot 1, the outcomes of Pilot Kick-Off Workshop were as follows: a User Journey from the perspective of a politician in Berlin who decides on measures for small lakes (see overview in Appendix A1, Figure 35) and an interface design of the Lake Splashboard tool that can support this user journey (see Appendix A1).

An interactive Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the Lake Splashboard tool was developed using the tool Figma¹ and is available at: <https://www.figma.com/proto/RnLaU99CKtBUi3CP0OPk2Y/%5BAD4GD%5D-Pilot-1---State-2?type=design&node-id=22-70&t=DwRavAyIrOVdpn6K-1&scaling=scale-down&page-id=0%3A1&starting-point-node-id=22%3A70&mode=design> (password: AD4GD).

- USER JOURNEY FOR PILOT 1

The pilot 1 User Journey is defined from the perspective of a decision maker in Berlin, the “Berlin Districts Lake Manager”, and comprises four phases: Trigger, Lake Index, Plausibility check (optional) and Decision making. *NB: the ‘Lake Index’ referred to in this user journey and in Figure 35 has since evolved to be defined as the WAI and / or WQI, and should be interpreted as referring to these proposed indicators.*

Phase 1: Trigger

The starting point of the User Journey could be an Email from the Senate to a district asking for scientific evidence about which lakes are most urgently in need of action in order to distribute resources for the rehabilitation of particular small lakes in Berlin. In other cases, citizens or NGO members may call to complain about dirty lakes or bad smelling water. Some lakes with high risk in terms of water quality and water availability are also known to the Berlin District Managers and they may want to monitor their status with little effort.

A second possible starting point for the journey is rainwater management, which will be one of the major regulatory and city planning tasks in Berlin in the next decade. Urban planning activities around the small lakes may also require decision making support.

¹ <https://www.figma.com/>

Phase 2: Lake Index

When using Lake Splashboard, the Berlin Districts Lake Manager will be able to select a lake in question, inspect available lake data (including a table with current estimated nutrient levels and water availability), and choose a time frame (the shorter – the higher the uncertainty) to compare the seasonal evolution of water quality and water levels. The tool will also display a Lake Index currently being developed by KWB (see Sections 3.2 and 3.5 for details) that will be calculated based on Sentinel-2 data from the Copernicus Data Ecosystem, weather data from Deutscher Wetterdienst, German Meteorological Service, and IoT sensor data as appropriate. At present, CitSci data, e.g., photos of lake water level, is of low priority. Access to some of this data will potentially be restricted and will require appropriate authentication. The Lake Index and all supplemental information (raw measurement data) will be used to help in decision making when distributing the resources.

Phase 3: Plausibility check (optional)

The Lake Manager can take water samples or level observations to validate the Lake Index. They can thus provide feedback on the Lake Index quality to KWB and the Lake Index can be iteratively improved.

Phase 4: Decision making

The last step is to decide how to allocate the rehabilitation measures and which lakes to tackle first. To aid this decision, Lake Splashboard should indicate the type of rehabilitation needed along with clear urgency ranking based on the Lake Index. The tool should additionally provide functionality for generating and sharing a report (e.g., a simple print function or a link to a predefined Lake Splashboard view).

3.8 TECHNICAL COMPONENTS REQUIRED TO SUPPORT THE PILOT STUDY

The above analysis identified several technical components needed to support the workflows and data pipelines of the water pilot study. These are summarised in Figure 6, and labelled according to whether a solution already exists, needs to be adapted or must be developed within the AD4GD project. In the latter case, the diagram identifies the section of this report where any relevant development is documented.

Pilot 1: Water Quality

AD4GD

Figure 6: Water pilot technical components.

Several sources of data for the pilot are already available and accessible via open and standardised Application Programming Interfaces (APIs); the key gaps are in the specific measurements for smaller lakes which will allow verification and calibration of any models to their specific conditions. IoT and CitSci data pipelines are to be developed within the coming year (see Section 3).

In situ sensor data from the Senate's 'Wasserportal' can be accessed immediately in order to prepare example data ingestion and analysis pipelines. To enable this, a more standardised service format for ingested data streams will be employed (STA), building on the already-available FROST server implementation² (6.5). The data to be ingested must be semantically enriched in order to enhance its value in the GDDS, and for this, bespoke code is being developed within the project (Sections 6.3, 6.4, 6.5) which will draw on semantic terms curated in an extension of the OGC RAINBOW server (Section 6.12).

The experimental data ingestion and analysis is to be hosted and developed by ATOS on a platform with a Minio data lake and instances of KubeFlow and MFlow to develop and deploy Machine Learning (ML) modelling workflows. Working in collaboration with KWB, ATOS will develop and verify prediction models first for water availability and later for water quality, leading to pipelines which can deliver a well-defined and well-documented WAI and WQI (Section 6.8).

The 'Lake Splashboard' UI (Section 3.7) will be developed by FIT as the client through which a GDDS user will access this service to trigger an analysis and retrieve/visualise output data and metadata. Metadata for the inputs, for any published outputs and for the analysis services will be published on a Geonetwork instance (Section 6.9). This ISO-format data may further be transformed to Geospatial Data Catalog Vocabulary (GeoDCAT) to amplify the discoverability of the resources across a wider range of tools and federated catalogues (Section 6.10).

² <https://fraunhoferiosb.github.io/FROST-Server/sensorthingsapi/requestingData/STA-Data-Model.html>.

4 PILOT 2 - BIODIVERSITY

4.1 INITIAL PILOT RATIONALE AND DESIGN

Biodiversity conservation, and ecological connectivity in particular, is a fundamental milestone in global and European policies strategies. The European Green Deal specifically declares “protecting nature” as one of the 11 pillars. Moreover, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 advocates for the “creation and integration of ecological corridors as part of a TransEuropean Nature Network to prevent genetic isolation, allowing for species migration and maintenance and enhancing of healthy ecosystems”. The Convention on Biodiversity (CBD) post-2020 targets, declares in the “Milestone A.1. Net gain in the area, connectivity and integrity of natural systems of at least 5% Target 2. Ensure that at least 20% of degraded terrestrial ecosystems are under restoration, ensuring connectivity and focusing on priority ecosystems”. Finally, the well known Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) targets and indicators, promotes in the Goal 15 to “Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss”.

Functional landscape connectivity (FLC) reflects the ability of species to pass through landscape, moving between patches of habitats (Auffret et al. 2017). FLC for animal and plant dispersal is a fundamental consideration for national, regional and local governments in making strategic spatial decisions about protected area networks, industrial / residential zoning, agricultural practice regulations and incentives, and land remediation. These governmental stakeholders seek standardised metrics on the state and protection of biodiversity for international reporting. At the same time, they need accessible information products, that are more sensitive to local contexts, to facilitate dialogue about policy with stakeholders in the countryside such as farmers.

Approaches to quantifying connectivity vary from graph-based models (e.g. Biodiversity Indicators Partnership’s ProtConn) that generalise the exploration and exploitation of intervening matrix, to remote sensing derived approaches that represent habitats as a continuous field classified according to their accessibility and reciprocal affinity (such as the Ecological Connectivity Index currently used in Catalonia). ProtConn statistics for protected areas are available at country and ecoregion level through the Joint Research Centre’s (JRC) Digital Observatory of Protected Areas³, and are accepted internationally for reporting progress against Aichi Target 11 and the Sustainable Development Goal 15. However it is difficult for regional governments to access the data and services which would allow consistent connectivity metrics to be re-generated and downscaled across a complex landscape mosaic which must support food security and a range of other human uses. There is significant potential for estimates of FLC to be validated with IoT, sensors in the field, and CitSci observations that verify the usage of corridors by some target species. However, the integration of such data into workflows mainly based on satellite and cadastral data is complex and not well supported by existing tools.

This pilot aims to deliver FAIR and scalable computation services based on Data Cube technologies (e.g. Open Data Cube), dockerising of applications, etc., for assessing FLC. It intends to integrate CitSci, administrative, satellite, socio-economic and IoT data streams, and AI analysis services. It is led by CREAM, with technical support from AU.

³ <https://dopa-explorer.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>,
<https://research.aston.ac.uk/en/publications/the-digital-observatory-for-protected-areas-dopa-explorer-10>,
<https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/static/dopa/static/dopa/files/factsheets/en/DOPA%20Factsheet%20C1%20EN%20Connectivity.pdf>

4.2 SCOPING AND IDENTIFICATION OF FOCUS

Pilot 2 covers a case study area of Catalonia, Spain. However, methods harnessed to compute the functional landscape connectivity of species' habitats rely partially on assumptions about maximum migration distances and minimum patch area. Bearing in mind that the officially established borderline of Catalonia cannot be considered a barrier for species to migrate to other regions or a divider for transboundary habitat patches, the initial data used to compute connectivity have been extended to a larger spatial extent than Catalonia, covering most of the possible migration distances of rare and endangered species, according to previous studies devoted to European habitats (Zalewski et al. 2003, Ferreras et al. 2004, Byrne et al. 2014, et al.). As an illustration, many protected areas important for rare and endangered species cross the Catalanian boundary with France and the Aragon province of Spain (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Land-use/land-cover types, intersected by formal boundaries of countries, regions and protected areas.

4.3 RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

Based on the project findings to date, the following stakeholder groups were identified in the context of Pilot 1. Their high priority needs are documented in the form of User Stories.

The *Territory and Sustainability Department of the Catalan Government (DTES)* works on many topics around the environment in Catalonia including topics like biodiversity, meteorology, energy and more. With regard to biodiversity, they are involved, among other things, in the development of strategies for protected areas as well as in planning new infrastructure. They are working with the concept of ecological connectivity and provide data on their website. In addition, they are also responsible for the reporting of biodiversity to international organisations. The needs of this stakeholder are not yet clear, which is why further discussions need to be planned with them in the future.

Researchers at CREAM are requested by governmental institutes for their expertise on biodiversity and cartography. They have to perform studies to support the decision makers but they also work on other biodiversity and cartography research projects.

“As a researcher, I want to provide a tested methodology to retrieve FLC in order that decision makers can take environmental information into account when planning for new infrastructures.”

“As a researcher, I want to provide a tested methodology that can be transferred to other regions to support decision makers.”

Biodiversity CitSci communities/platforms

iNaturalist is an online social network of people sharing biodiversity information to help each other learn about nature⁴. It's also a crowdsourced species identification system and an organism occurrence recording tool. Even though ordinary citizens are able to upload their own data via a mobile app, these records undergo verification by experienced users, including those with a biological background.

It is important to consider licences while using any *iNaturalist* data (in most cases it is CC BY-NC 4.0⁵)

GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) is an international network and data infrastructure aiming at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all organisms⁶. Unlike *iNaturalist*, only confirmed institutes and organisations, including CitSci projects and *iNaturalist* verified Research-grade Observations, can publish data at GBIF. Therefore, GBIF data may be considered more plausible and accurate. Moreover, the GBIF API provides a way to publish and query data on GBIF.org, including information about species and higher taxons, occurrences, GBIF-indexed references, visual representations (maps), data validation, etc..

Fototrampes Mamífers Catalunya (part of the international MammalWeb project) is an open-access portal providing access to data obtained from photographic tracking (phototrapping)⁷. The portal aims to become a CitSci project, where any user with a camera has an opportunity to upload photos taken (users called "trackers") and review and classify uploaded data in order to increase the reliability of species identification (users called "spotters").

4.4 INDICATORS AND METRICS

As of the time of writing, the term “Connectivity of terrestrial ecosystem habitat types” is included in the list of EuropaBON Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs)⁸. EBV products described include distance to nearest neighbour patch, habitat within specific buffer area, graph-related indices and other connectivity metrics with a spatial resolution from 10 x 10m to 100 x 100 m, which precisely matches the scope and coverage of Pilot 2. Following developments within the AD4GD project, this term is recorded on the OGC RAINBOW⁹ server (see Section 6.12) and links back to the corresponding reference to the EuropaBON Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs).

⁴ *iNaturalist*. <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/about>

⁵ free to share, copy, redistribute, adapt, transform material in any format. Credit must be given (e.g. link to licence and statement about adaptations). no commercial use allowed.

⁶ GBIF. <https://www.gbif.org/what-is-gbif>

⁷ Fototrampes Mamífers Catalunya | Grup Felis ICHN. <https://grupfelis-ichn.iec.cat/fototrampes-catalunya/>

⁸ [Terrestrial Connectivity of terrestrial ecosystem habitat types: \(EuropaBON/EBV-Descriptions\)](https://github.com/EuropaBON/EBV-Descriptions/wiki/Terrestrial-Connectivity-of-terrestrial-ecosystem-habitat-types). <https://github.com/EuropaBON/EBV-Descriptions/wiki/Terrestrial-Connectivity-of-terrestrial-ecosystem-habitat-types>

⁹ The OGC Rainbow Definitions Server (EBVs). <https://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/object?uri=http%3A//w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ebv>

Amongst other established FLC metrics that may be used to enrich the semantic dimension of such datasets, the following indicators are endorsed by the Biodiversity Indicator Partnership¹⁰:

- Protected Connected (ProtConn) strongly related to the connectivity of protected areas. This metric is generally computed at the level of country and ecoregion (Saura et al. 2017) which is insufficient for the scope and spatial resolution of Pilot 2.
- Protected Area Connectedness Index (PARC-Connectedness) computed through pixel-by-pixel estimation of connectivity with protected landscapes and primary vegetation on non-protected areas (Hoskins et al. 2016, Di Marco et al. 2019). This index with values from 0 to 1 provides a simple representation of connectivity which may be implemented at all levels of spatial resolutions, starting from 1 km. However, the estimations of this index have not been updated since 2019.

The broad variety of other indices that may be used to compute FLC at the regional level (including Catalonia), is discussed below in Section 4.6.

4.5 INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL FACTORS

External factors that might be affecting FLC could be explored from Article 17 of the Habitats Directive list of pressures and threats¹¹.

In this last case, the main categories of pressures are:

- PA. Agriculture related practices
- PB. Forestry related practices
- PC. Extraction of resources (minerals, peat, non-renewable energy resources)
- PD. Energy production processes and related infrastructure development
- PE. Development and operation of transport systems
- PF. Development, construction and use of residential, commercial, industrial and recreational infrastructure and areas
- PG. Extraction and cultivation of biological living resources (other than agriculture and forestry)
- PH. Military action, public safety measures, and other human intrusions
- PI. Alien and problematic species
- PJ. Climate change
- PK. Mixed source pollution
- PL. Human-induced changes in water regimes
- PM. Geological events, natural processes and catastrophes

Each of these categories are split in many subcategories of pressures or external factors. From this list, we identify the most relevant pressures in the area of the Pilot 2 and try to discover whether there is information or not on that pressure.

Some of the datasets that currently exist related to external factors in Catalonia, are:

- River pollution
- Agricultural intensification
- Length of accumulated roads per pixel
- Wind energy production
- Fishing pressure
- Population data (1982 - to the present)
- Livestock load data (1982 - to the present)
- Recurrence of drought (2010-2015)

¹⁰ Biodiversity Indicators Partnership. <https://www.bipindicators.net/>

¹¹

https://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/help/habitats_art17/Reporting2025/List%20of%20pressures%20and%20threats%20for%20reporting%202019-2024%20v1.1.xlsx

- Number of invasive species
- Risk of invasion by alien species
- Probability of combustion per pixel
- Number of fires
- Distances to road infrastructures
- Superficial schooling

Some of these datasets may only exist for a certain date and thus might not be useful to analyse trends.

According to the Spanish Strategy for the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Biodiversity, erosion (more than 18% of Spain is affected by soil loss rates of over 50 Tm per Ha/year), pollution of water bodies and streams (more than 11% is highly polluted), and wetland drainage (more than 60% in less than 50 years) are amongst the main pressures on natural habitats¹².

Despite being vulnerable to the multiple pressures, the overlap between Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA) and Catalanian protected areas is 61.7%- slightly below the average national level (64.4%). Meanwhile, Catalonia and Southern France are extremely abundant in rare and endangered species that are endemic which once again proves the relevance and importance of biodiversity studies there¹³.

4.6 METHODOLOGIES AND TOOLS

4.6.1 HABITAT CONNECTIVITY

Terrestrial connectivity accounts for a large history, in Catalonia (Marulli and Mallarach 2005). However, two complementary approaches are widely known to assess the connectivity of terrestrial habitats:

- Habitat connectivity based on a structural approach (Calabrese & Fagan 2004) resulting from assessing the spatial pattern of habitats with no information on organism behaviour.
- Biological/functional connectivity, based on an organismic/functional approach including information on dispersal abilities of the modelled organisms.

Even though these broadly used methods to assess terrestrial and marine connectivity are close (e.g., network analysis or graph theory), marine connectivity strongly depends on biophysical modelling, including physics of the ocean, rather than classifications of use and cover (LULC) derived mainly from remote sensing data.

Two frameworks to assess habitat connectivity will be evaluated and compared in this pilot:

1. Integral terrestrial connectivity index (ICT) computed through MiraMon software (Marulli and Mallarach 2005).
2. Indices based on graph theory and computed mostly via Graphab (Foltête et al., 2021) or Conefor (Saura and Torné, 2009) software.

Each of these has been applied earlier to a number of academic studies in various fields (Pascual-Hortal and Saura 2008, Foltête et al. 2012b, Balni et al. 2020, Lizana-Ciudad et al. 2021). Graph theory applications can provide explicit and plausible computations of connectivity between habitat patches, but may be complicated by choice of proper indexes (Foltête et al. 2012b) and computation time (Foltête et al. 2012a) (to address this resource constraint, Graphab can be parallelised through the Message Passing Interface (MPI) framework on computer clusters (Foltête et al., 2021). Meanwhile it has been found that ICT computations on MiraMon require significant resources as well (for further details see Section 6.7).

¹² CBD Strategy and Action Plan. Spain. <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/es/es-nbsap-01-pl-en.pdf>

¹³ State of Biodiversity in Spain. https://www.uicn.es/web/pdf/Estbio/CR_GENERAL.pdf

The first framework applied to this pilot (Pino 2012) includes three components or summands: connectivity within the focal patch (C_{1i}), connectivity between the same habitat patches (C_{2i}), and connectivity with patches of similar habitats (C_{3i}).

$$ICT_i = C_{1i} + C_{2i} + C_{3i}$$

These summands are calculated for discrete points in a regular matrix at a certain distance for the whole Catalonia. Calculations are performed taking a circular area of influence of 2500 m around each point.

The calculation takes into consideration the affinity and impedance among land-use/land-cover categories, which are defined by the suitability of landscape for species to pass through. These need to be known in advance, for instance, from expert knowledge or previous studies.

$$C_{3i} = \sum_{j \neq i} a_j A_j e^{-\alpha \cdot \delta_j}$$

Where:

α : is the mean dispersal coefficient. Through expert knowledge it has been estimated that general connectivity (of all organisms and processes in the landscape) is reduced to 5% at 2500 m distance. Thus, assuming an exponential decrease of connectivity, α is calculated as follows: $\alpha = -\ln(0.5)/2500$

A_j is the patch area

a_j : is the mean affinity value of each habitat type with respect to each habitat i , also set up by expert knowledge from indirect information about the number of organisms shared between habitats. C_{1i} and C_{2i} are degenerate cases of C_{3i} , in which mean affinity between habitat types is 1.

δ_j is the cost distance to the habitat patches, obtained from the Euclidean distance of each point to the patches weighted by impedance values, calculated from mean impedance values per habitat

The pixel-by-pixel calculations described above enhanced with two matrices of habitat affinity and impedances has been implemented in MiraMon GIS software via Terrestrial Connectivity Index (ICT) (Marulli and Mallarach 2005).

The second framework mentioned above is often implemented through Graphab (Foltête et al., 2021)¹⁴ or Conefor (Saura and Torné, 2009)¹⁵ software which are amongst the most powerful open-access applications (see Appendix A4) providing the opportunity to compute connectivity indices at various scales: global, regional, local and also to compute a delta which considers the relative importance of each graph element once any element is removed from a graph).

Both tools are based on graph theory and provide users with explicit and complicated computations considering links (or edges) between nodes of graph representing centroids of habitats (or patches) (Urban et al. 2009). Apart from GUI, Graphab and Conefor may be used via command-line interface to process batches of input data and to model transformations in connectivity induced by natural and human-driven changes in land use and land cover.

¹⁴ Graphab. <https://sourcesup.renater.fr/www/graphab/en/home.html>

¹⁵ Conefor. <http://www.conefor.org/>

Since specific parameters of biota dispersal are considered in this Pilot (maximum dispersal distance, minimum habitat patch area, impedance and affinity of landscape), our approach is referred to as functional landscape connectivity (FLC).

Besides the software described above, a wide range of tools are used to compute fragmentation of habitats, which is strongly interdependent with connectivity but is not covered by Pilot 2. The most prominent are:

- Fragstats focused on numerous landscape metrics - area, edges and their contrast, shape of landscape patches, statistics of core areas within patches, aggregated indices (including broadly used effective mesh size, landscape division index, splitting index etc.) (McGarigal et al., 2023).
- GuidosToolbox based on morphological spatial pattern analysis and used mainly to distinguish binary images, for instance, to detect changes in forest cover or reveal connecting structures between landscape patches (Vogt and Riitters, 2023).

However, pilot 2 is focused on the computation of functional connectivity indices, not fragmentation.

4.6.2 REMOTE SENSING

The crucial input data to calculate any FLC indices in both MiraMon and Graphab is a land-use/land-cover (LULC) map. The Land Use Land Cover Map of Catalonia (MUCSC) created by CREA, UAB and the Generalitat de Catalunya (González-Guerrero and Pons 2020) has been used as the main input data source. This map is obtained from the automatic classification of Landsat and Sentinel-2 images.

To avoid edge effects in the ICT calculation, the MUCSC has been combined with three ancillary LULC maps in the borders of the region (Table 1), resulting in 8 extended LULC maps (Figure 8).

- The CORINE land cover map for the areas of France
- The Land Cover Map of Andorra for Andorra.
- The Spanish SIOSE Map for the areas of Aragón and València.
-

Table 1: Timestamps of raw LULC data which were combined.

	MUCSC	CORINE (France)	SIOSE (Aragón and València)	Andorra
Most suitable correspondence dates	1987	1990		1995
	1992			
	1997	2000		
	2002	2000	2005	2012
	2007	2006		
	2012	2012	2011	
	2017	2018	2014	
	2022	2018	2017 (SIOSE High Resolution)	2012

Figure 8: Series of extended LULC maps (Catalonia and neighbouring regions of Spain, France and Andorra).

A simplified classification is executed to perform the analysis of the ICT index between the final LULC categories (see Appendix A2). Thus, two levels of LULC classification are implemented: initial classification (25) and merged LULC classes (7) aggregating the LULC variety, five of which are ecologically meaningful in terms of functional habitat connectivity (forests, meadows and shrublands, woody crops, herbaceous crops, aquatic environments).

Extended LULC data have been used to compute FLC indices in both MiraMon and Graphab, along with LULC derivatives – impedances (both tools) and affinities (MiraMon only), based on expert knowledge.

4.6.3 CITIZEN SCIENCE

To incorporate CitSci data related to biodiversity and connectivity into Pilot 2, two sources are currently being considered: Open Street Map (OSM)¹⁶ and GBIF¹⁷. The first source contains the explicit data mostly on socioeconomic aspects in specific areas, mostly urban ones. However, this data may be applied to the connectivity studies to rectify LULC maps. GBIF occurrences data, in contrast, is directly related to the connectivity topic and may be used to reveal patches of habitats affected by any potential changes in LULC.

4.6.4 INGESTION OF OPEN STREET MAP DATA

Despite being the main source of geospatial data to compute connectivity, LULC data derived from the remote sensing have been considered a non-exhaustive source to gauge all crucial barriers for organisms to migrate. It has been revealed that (Figure 9):

1. Many waterways, especially small rivers and streams are not consistent, being split into segmented patches due to seasonal changes (drying rivers or dense canopy cover overshadowing parts of water bodies) or too small waterway width to be detected by classification of satellite imagery.
2. Railways and roads with tarmac pavements and considerable traffic have not been detected by imagery classification even after series of refinements and corrections.

Meanwhile, such human-made (roads and railways) and natural (waterways) barriers may considerably restrict opportunities for organisms to migrate. Therefore, it becomes necessary to provide the consistent representation of barriers to avoid any “loopholes” which do not exist at all. At the same time, residential and industrial areas between patches of habitats that seriously affect migration are performed considerably better and do not require any corrections.

¹⁶ Open Street Map. <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

¹⁷ GBIF Occurrences. <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search>

Figure 9: Series of extended LULC maps (Catalonia and neighbouring regions of Spain, France and Andorra).

To enrich raster LULC data, the OSM portal has been accessed to gather reliable vector data, produced by the public, licensed under the Open Data Commons Open Database License and being in line with CitSci principles. The technical procedure is described in Section 6.7.

According to one of the conditions of preprocessing for computing connectivity, OSM data are used if the user is not able to incorporate any other reliable vector data on connectivity barriers. Nonetheless, this part of Pilot 2 workflow will be advanced further through regional vector data from Catalanian government¹⁸ regarding human-made and natural connectivity barriers.

4.6.5 GBIF INGESTION

Through this pilot, AD4GD wants to explore to what degree CitSci and community-based monitoring (CBM) can contribute to better understand how terrestrial species are affected by habitats lack of connectivity. Thus, we have explored several CitSci networks gathering species occurrences with the intention to combine these species counting datasets with the connectivity maps elaborated within the project.

GBIF is the main data research infrastructure gathering hundreds of millions of records from >800 institutions worldwide and covers > 1.6 million species [#ref¹⁹]. However, most of the records are for birds occurrences, and the accumulation rates of nonbird species occurrence records is not improving, and even potentially declining, over the past three decades [#ref²⁰].

¹⁸ Gencat. <https://agricultura.gencat.cat/ca/serveis/cartografia-sig/>

¹⁹ Chandler M, See L, Copas K et al. (2016) Contribution of citizen science towards international biodiversity monitoring. *Biological Conservation*. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.biocon.2016.09.004

²⁰ Amano T, Lamm JDL & Sutherland WJ (2016) Spatial Gaps in Global Biodiversity Information and the Role of Citizen Science. *BioScience* 66: 393–400. Available at: doi:10.1093/biosci/biw022

To compare occurrences recorded by professionals and non-professionals representing CitSci, a dataset on rare and endangered mammal species in Spain (excluding the LC category by IUCN – Least Concern) has been retrieved through the GBIF API (ref. Github) with a total of 80758 records.

To reveal any difference in quality of datasets from professionals and CitSci representatives, share of records with issue flags by various institutions (70) and datasets (130) has been compared (for further details see on Github²¹). These institutions and datasets have been matched with a new data attribute – “provenanceType”. The derived “provenanceType” has been filled with one of the following text values: “professional”, “non-professional”, “mixed” (Figure 10). However, such “provenanceType” should be ideally based not on the type of institution, as datasets uploaded even by professional institutions may contain data bunches derived from laymen. It becomes obvious that data from academic institutions may be enriched with the CitSci data without valid references to the original source. Therefore, keys “publishingOrgKey”, “institutionCode”, “rightsHolder” are not able to provide a perfect match with the actual provenance of data in line with CitSci or professional activities.

At the same time, the “datasetKey” provides more explicit descriptions on data provenance, even though it is not possible to track the level of expertise of the recorder. To compare the reliability of data recorded by professionals and non-professionals (including CitSci projects), the number of issues (from 0 to 5) across these data sources has been compared. It has been revealed that data from mixed and non-professional datasets (Figure 10) is characterised by an even lower mean number of issues per occurrence record (0.42 and 1.71 respectively compared to 1.75 for professional datasets). Therefore, the relevance of occurrences data from non-professional and mixed sources, including CitSci projects mentored and verified by scientific community, should not be underestimated as all types of data sources are abundant in issues (especially old records published by professionals), whereas their relative importance is different (for instance, rounded coordinates will likely bring an inaccuracy to the computation of local FLC, but fuzzy matching to taxon will not reduce the accuracy).

Thus, data derived from CitSci representatives is incorporated and integrated in GBIF datasets. Moreover, its trustworthiness and plausibility may be higher than records published by professional institutions. However, the general provenance of GBIF data from CitSci contributors may be complicated to track. In keeping with the semantic focus of the AD4GD project, we will in future explore the feasibility of representing these ‘*produced-by*’ relationships using the PROV Ontology (PROV-O)²² in addition to the ISO standard of lineage documentation through process steps.

²¹ GBIF data provenance analysis. <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2/tree/main/gbif>

²²The PROV Ontology (PROV-O). <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

Figure 10: The provenance (left) and the number of issues (right) of occurrences datasets on mammal rare and endangered species in Catalonia (excluding the LC category by IUCN - Least Concern).

4.6.6 IN SITU SENSORS

The approach used in Pilot 2 to compute Terrestrial Connectivity is purely based on habitat (or LULC) affinities and frictions (impedances), but is agnostic on the behaviour or real affectation to terrestrial species. In order to increase the plausibility of the developed connectivity computation workflow (see Section 6.7), information coming from CS and/or *in situ* sensors will be incorporated into the Pilot 2. This kind of information (along with the occurrence observations by citizens), could be useful in 2 ways:

- On one hand, readjust the affinities/impedances values for the concrete species based on the real knowledge regarding their traits and habitat specificity.
- On the other hand, combine the existing information on the developed LULC-derived connectivity maps with real numbers of decrease/increase of some species, to better understand if fragmentation is affecting the species behaviour or not.

In the case of *in situ* sensors, AD4GD will try to test some own camera traps, but, meanwhile, the project is in contact with Catalan organisations, such as FotoTrampeig Mamífers Catalunya²³ where citizens share their photos coming from their own camera traps, and being part of a bigger and international organisation, MammalWeb²⁴. Other similar organisations, are Projecte Liró²⁵ and the Atles de Mamífers de Catalunya²⁶. With them, we will analyse the use and share of this kind of data, how it is stored and securely shared, and how this can be connected in a standard way ready to be used in a Data Space. Specific standards for exchange of this information are being analysed, i.e., Camtrap DP: an open standard for the FAIR exchange and archiving of camera trap data (Bubnicki et al. 2023).

²³ <https://grupfelis-ichn.iec.cat/fototrampeig-catalunya/>

²⁴ <https://www.mammalweb.org/en/discover-view>

²⁵ <https://www.lirons.org/exploreu>

²⁶ <https://observatorinatura.cat/atles-mamifers/>

4.6.7 SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA

The role of socio-economic data in FLC is something to be analysed in Pilot 2. To this end, socio-economic datasets coming from the Catalan Government will be included in the experiments, from population data to agricultural information from the cadaster or the CAP (EU's common agricultural policy). The HiperMapa server (<https://sig.gencat.cat/visors/hipermapa.html>) from the Catalan Administration will be carefully explored for new datasets, as well as the interviews to be held with them as stakeholders in the project.

To date, socioeconomic data have been implemented into the Pilot 2 to refine and enrich LULC data through OSM datasets (see above Section 4.6.3). Even though they include natural features as well, human-constructed objects tend to be covered more extensively in OSM.

Once the available and relevant datasets are agreed, then it will be considered whether to incorporate them into the DataCube, or use them only as WMS/WCS protocol in the browser. Standard ways to connect to each dataset will also be explored for a common and integrated DataSpace.

4.7 UPDATED PROBLEM AND SOLUTION STATEMENT

Based on the project findings to date, the following updated Problem and Solution Statements were generated for the Pilot 2 Case.

Updated Problem Statement

Functional landscape connectivity (FLC) is essential for supporting gene flow between populations, enabling species to adapt to environmental changes, and promoting ecosystem resilience. It is a critical consideration for conservation planning, land-use management, and sustainable development to ensure that habitats are interconnected, and wildlife can move freely across the landscape.

As said, FLC is important when it comes to strategic spatial decision making about new infrastructure, protected areas, industrial and residential zoning, agricultural practice regulations and incentives and many more. However, existing pre-computed indices are often only available on country or ecoregion level (e.g. through the European Commission's Digital Observatory for Protected Areas²⁷) and regional governments may find it difficult to access the data and analysis services required to make more locally or thematically meaningful estimates. Today, decision makers are lacking information on FLC (for selected species) that is sensitive to the local context to make informed decisions in terms of biodiversity.

Our Solution Statement

To create a new tool for computing functional landscape connectivity of habitats based on existing and well-established methods and software (Graphab and MiraMon) to reach trade-offs between stakeholders or win-win situations considering LULC changes suggested by stakeholders or third parties.

The above mentioned decision making regarding new infrastructure, protected areas, industrial and residential zoning, agricultural practice regulations and incentives and many more can be supported by the BioConnect tool that shows the effects of changes on the FLC. The tool is described in Section 4.8.

4.8 END-USER TOOL DESCRIPTION

For Pilot 2, the outcomes of Pilot Kick-Off Workshop were as follows: two sequential User Journeys from the perspective of a researcher at CREAM and a technician in the Administration in Catalonia (see overview in Appendix A1, Figure 37 and Figure 38) and an interface design of the BioConnect tool that can support these user journeys (see Appendix A1).

²⁷

<https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/var/www/app/app/static/dopa/files/factsheets/en/DOPA%20Factsheet%20CI%20EN%20Connectivity.pdf>

An interactive Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the BioConnect tool was developed using the tool Figma and is available at: <https://www.figma.com/proto/npDbLQodT8OF74hIczQZuW/%5BAD4GD%5D-Pilot-2---Version-2?type=design&node-id=2007-140&t=nvyzaIcxHtiITXrF-1&scaling=scale-down&page-id=0%3A1&starting-point-node-id=2018%3A54&mode=design> (password: AD4GD).

- USER JOURNEY FOR PILOT 2

For Pilot 2, two User Journeys are defined from the perspectives of a researcher at CREAM and a technician in the Administration in Catalonia. User Journey 1 begins with the existing LULC raster maps and ends with the availability of multidimensional connectivity maps enriched with various data. User Journey 2 starts with the task of writing a report on the expansion of a planned infrastructure and ends with the planned construction of the infrastructure.

User Journey 1 - Researcher at CREAM

A researcher at CREAM has the goal to enrich LULC raster maps to build multidimensional connectivity maps. This user journey consists of 4 phases: Enrich maps with *in situ* data; Enrich maps with IoT data; Reorganisation of the data; Simplification of query.

Phase 1: Enrich maps with *in situ* data

To enrich LULC raster maps with *in situ* data, the researcher needs to investigate available data on vulnerable species. Among other things, the researcher wants to find out if different species have different friction values. There is a remaining question of how many species can be incorporated, but the researcher decides to focus on one species. The researcher downloads all existing data for this species using the GBIF API²⁸ (CSV file with occurrence, timestamp, position, etc.) and creates a species map using GIS.

Phase 2: Enrich maps with IoT data

The researcher might decide to install their own IoT devices (e.g., camera traps, radio tracking) to collect additional data; the location of the sensors will be decided based on species occurrence maps generated in Phase 1. Once installed, data on the positions of occurrence is collected (at present, it is not possible to record movements between locations). A number of questions that need to be considered include: “What is the format of the collected data (data complexity)?”, “Where to get training data for species recognition?”, “What is needed for species recognition in collected images?”. Data licensing and access rights must also be considered.

Phase 3: Reorganisation of the data (Data Cubes)

The researcher can then create data cubes using Open Data Cube²⁹ to produce raster maps enriched by all relevant collected data from different sources.

Phase 4: Simplification of query

All the information reorganised by means of the multidimensional Data Cube makes it now possible to perform queries in a more understandable and simplified manner to the BioConnect tool.

User Journey 2: Technician in the Administration in Catalonia

The technician in the Administration in Catalonia has the goal to write a report on the impact of a planned construction on the ecological connectivity. This user journey consists of 2 phases: Obtain ecological connectivity maps and Generate updated connectivity maps.

Phase 1: Obtain ecological connectivity maps

The researcher can use the BioConnect tool to select a geographic area and obtain connectivity maps (including species information where available).

²⁸ <https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/>

²⁹ <https://www.opendatacube.org/>

Phase 2: Generate updated connectivity maps

The researcher can then manipulate these connectivity maps by adding or deleting infrastructures to generate updated connectivity maps. The tool will keep a history of the original connectivity maps and the updated versions to enable the evaluation of how infrastructure changes affect the ecological connectivity.

4.9 TECHNICAL COMPONENTS REQUIRED TO SUPPORT THE PILOT STUDY

The above analysis identified several technical components needed to support the workflows and data pipelines of the biodiversity pilot study. These are summarised in Figure 11, and labelled according to whether a solution already exists, needs to be adapted or must be developed within the AD4GD project. In the latter case, the diagram identifies the section of this report where any relevant development is documented.

Figure 11: Biodiversity pilot technical components.

The core purpose of the pilot relies on a source of raster LULC data, which can be analysed through a few user-defined parameters with a reliable and accepted method to compute maps of FLC which will be returned to the user either for visualisation and reporting, or for further analysis. The BioConnect client that is proposed as the interface to this process is described in Section 4.8. A source of input LULC data already exists for the Catalonia region, and the classification methodology described in Section 3 allows repeatable production of comparable LULC maps across multiple timesteps. This facilitates powerful analyses which evaluate changes in FLC over time - a key environmental metric for reporting and strategic landscape planning, and for assessing the effects of infrastructure development. The multi-layer nature of the input LULC data and its natural grouping by theme calls for a data curation and publishing solution which can

handle and query grouped raster data layers, allowing a user to find and interact with the data in one place and with a single query, and to drill down through time for a selected region. For this reason, data cube technology has been investigated (see Section 6.6) as a solution for curating not just the input LULC data, but also the output stacks of FLC maps, since these also share spatial, thematic and semantic characteristics and should ideally be published, discovered and interrogated together. The processing functions of data cubes may in future allow LULC classification and other data transformations to be carried out on a cube, extending the pipeline to include SENTINEL EO data as inputs. This is not essential to deliver the pilot, but will be explored as described in Section 6.6.

The FLC calculations *per se* are to be carried out using two alternative approaches so that their results (which highlight different aspects of connectivity) can be compared and combined. The Graphab open source package is re-used to consider the landscape as a network of patches, while the open-source Miramon software applies a pixel neighbourhood approach that incorporates in more detail the characteristics of the intervening matrix between patches. Both packages will be dockerised in order to deliver a modular workflow which can ultimately be deployed on a range of platforms. An additional preprocessing step has been identified as necessary to enhance the quality of input data (see Section 6.7) by adding linear features which can act as barriers or conduits, and which are insufficiently captured by LULC maps based on typical multispectral EO data series. Infrastructure data from the Catalan government may be used for this specific pilot, but in order to make the workflow more generic and applicable to other domains, the user may alternatively choose to use CitSci data from OSM. The ingestion and use of this data is described in Section 6.7.

Computational resource constraints mean that it can be challenging to compute sets of connectivity scenarios over multiple hypothetical interventions and timesteps, or for multiple sets of species characteristics. To address this, the code developed by AU and CREAM has been designed to be parallelised for distributed / HPC computing where available. Metadata for the outputs and for the services themselves will be produced according to the ISO 19115 standard, including a documentation of lineage which captures the nature of the processing steps (see Section 6.9), and reference to relevant vocabulary terms representing Essential Variables (EVs) and other environmental concepts. Some of these terms may be found in repositories such as the LifeWatch EcoPortal, supporting multiple ontologies such as Darwin Core and Environmental Thesaurus, but those which are unavailable must be curated and hosted in our own semantic store (Section 6.12). The ISO metadata standard is widely used in the geospatial domain, but it is not the only standard underpinning environmental catalogues, and so a transformation to the widely-used GeoDCAT standards may be required in order to allow metadata federation to a wider range of global catalogues (Section 6.10).

An important source of biodiversity observation data for informing and validating ecological models is GBIF, which includes many CitSci observations from initiatives such as iNaturalist. The GBIF API allows easy access to map layers of occurrence via an OGC WMS API, and this is a likely route to access map layers for visualisation by the BioConnect Client. Alternatively, raw observation data for specified species and time periods may be accessed directly, and these will be explored in two different ways as shown on the diagram. GBIF are specifically working to produce species occurrence and suitability data cubes on demand as part of the work within our sister Horizon project, B3. We propose to ingest these cubes to demonstrate interoperability between systems and projects, by: (1) using the occurrence cubes as a benchmark for our assessments of FLC and to evaluate the predicted importance of key nodes and patches in the landscape, and (2) using species suitability maps as an INPUT to produce maps of FLC which are based explicitly on habitat suitability for a species, rather than using an LULC type as a proxy for habitat suitability. This second approach will allow an evaluation of the reliability of LULC as a cheap and widely-used proxy for habitat quality. The B3 data cubes will be hosted on a data cube and are likely to be available through standard WCS requests, which will allow us to exploit the investigations and insights from the work described in Section 6.6. However, this interaction with an external data provider also gives us an optional opportunity to test the functionality of data space connectors for delivering contractual data services (Section 6.2). Since this is an

alternative route for data access, it is a low-risk strategy for testing GDDS components while not jeopardising the progress of the pilot.

GBIF APIs are extensive, and the occurrence data they offer conforms to the Darwin Core standard. However, there are opportunities for further semantic enrichment by experimentally mapping this output to additional terms to produce Sensor Things API (STA) - or STAplus-compliant data, as described in Sections 6.3, 6.4, and 6.5. An STA / STAplus approach will also be taken to publication of any camera trap data which we may be able to access or produce within the project (still under discussion). Camera trap data has the potential to verify the usage of landscape features by key species of interest, but requires edge processing to reduce the bandwidth and data volume returned. This is the most experimental part of the pilot, and is still under active discussion, but will almost certainly be able to exploit on-sensor edge processing functions and sensors developed within the Cos4Cloud project.

5 PILOT 3 – AIR QUALITY

This pilot study originally centred on the broad topic of climate change and greenhouse gas emissions. However, given the extensive scope of this subject, we have chosen to refine the study's focus to specifically address air quality and its impact on health. With this updated, narrower focus the study aims to facilitate a comprehensive exploration of air pollution challenges and their health implications.

5.1 INITIAL PILOT RATIONALE AND DESIGN

Curbing greenhouse gas emissions and monitoring progress and effectiveness of mitigation policies is a key need in the context of the UNFCCC Paris Agreement. Countries in Europe and in the world have committed to report their emissions and about progress towards implementation of their nationally determined contributions. As part of the European GD, the EC has tasked the Copernicus programme to support the monitoring and verification process of Member State countries by implementing an ambitious system based on Earth Observation -the future CO2M (CO2 Monitoring) satellite constellation- and very advanced processing systems in order to derive emissions estimates from measured atmospheric concentrations through so-called “inverse modelling” techniques. A number of European Research and Innovation projects (CHE, VERIFY and CoCO2 to mention the most directly relevant) have supported or are supporting the required underpinning research. Robustness, transparency and quality of the emissions estimates are pivotal and a growing variety of *in situ* observations could in principle be used for validation purposes or even as input for the inversion either for assimilation or as a priori information. Integration of many sources of observation is essential in order to ensure that all relevant available information is eventually integrated for providing the best possible input to reporting and to policy design and monitoring. In the context of the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), this pilot focuses especially on evaluating the possible added value of socio-economic (e.g. traffic counts, energy production and transfer) and IoT (low-cost sensors) for estimating greenhouse gas concentrations and emissions in Europe. ECMWF leads the task, building upon activities already in place to provide a CO2 Monitoring and Verification Support capacity, with workflows that do not currently include IoT sources and could include more socio-economic data, particularly in real-time.

5.2 UPDATED PILOT RATIONALE

For decades, ambient air pollution has been one of the greatest challenges for protecting human health. For example, air pollution is responsible for various (including chronic) respiratory diseases (such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma) and for cardiovascular diseases (like high blood pressure). Moreover, studies indicate correlations between air pollution and other diseases such as dementia/Alzheimer's, diabetes, and cancers (e.g., lung cancer, breast cancer). It is estimated that air pollution leads to an excess mortality rate of about 8.79 million per year worldwide, which exceeds that of tobacco smoking. Against this backdrop, the WHO recently decided to further tighten the limits for air pollutants like PM2.5, PM10, NO2, and ozone.

To ensure compliance with these limits, systematic observations of these components are necessary. A problem is that the spatial and temporal variability of air pollution is highly variable and complex. As a result, the current, point-based measurement networks are too sparse and thus not representative in many areas. Also, the set-up, maintenance, and operation of these networks are very time-consuming and cost-intensive.

In this context, IoT data from networks of low-cost sensors (LCS) can make a decisive contribution to a better understanding of local air pollution. Particularly in CitSci projects, these sensors are purchased, installed, and maintained by citizens, eliminating costs for downstream data processing. Although these sensors do not achieve the accuracy of reference measurements, their high number and the associated high spatial resolution provide a much more representative picture of air pollution (especially in neglected areas like residential areas), and thus may allow for better verification of mitigation strategies from local politicians. The low cost of these instruments also creates the possibility for local communities to get involved, thereby increasing interest in this topic.

In this pilot study, we primarily want to investigate the extent to which the data from these LCS can be used to predict air quality or whether there is any additional benefit from these data for air pollution forecasting systems. We will initially focus on the observations of particulate matter (specifically PM10 and PM2.5) as these data are already available in large quantities, are easily accessible, and are simulated within the CAMS (regional) air quality model system. If data on nitrogen oxides (i.e. NO₂, NO) and/or ozone become available, it would be possible to extend the investigations to these trace gases. The insights gained from these investigations could then be used in further studies to determine the potential of IoT/LCS measurements of greenhouse gases (GHG) and eventually contribute to the determination of greenhouse gas emissions.

5.3 SCOPING AND IDENTIFICATION OF FOCUS

In Pilot 3, we focus on the application and analysis of IoT data for air quality monitoring and investigate how these sensors perform in regions with distinct air pollution profiles. The regions of Benelux and Northern Italy, notably the Po Valley, have been selected due to their unique environmental challenges and diverse sources of air pollution.

- Benelux Region (Belgium, Netherlands, Luxembourg): The Benelux region presents a unique air pollution profile characterised by a mix of emissions from urban areas, agriculture, industry, and (road) traffic. Cities such as Brussels, Antwerp, and Amsterdam are known for their high levels of nitrogen oxides (Nox) and particulate matter (PM) arising from these sources. Moreover, the unique geography of this region is a crucial factor and the impact of weather conditions, like wind, will be observed. While the region has notable urban centres with high population density, it is also characterised by strong agricultural activities, which play a role in its overall pollution levels.
- Northern Italy (Po Valley): The Po Valley is another region with a distinctive air pollution profile. Due to its geographical positioning and climatic conditions, this area experiences high levels of pollutants like ozone, particulate matter, and Nox. The pollution here is mainly compounded by factors such as industrial emissions and vehicular traffic, along with the valley's tendency to trap air pollutants.

Overall, the aim is to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of IoT sensors across these regions with differing pollution profiles. By comparing IoT data with that from established reference stations, we will gain insights into the spatial and temporal resolution of IoT sensors, their accuracy, and their effectiveness in providing detailed understanding of air quality variations in diverse environmental settings.

Additionally, a key objective is to investigate the potential of IoT data for delivering information on air pollution with high spatial resolution, particularly regarding its impact on human health. This involves analysing how IoT sensors can help in identifying and monitoring pollution hotspots and understanding the health implications of exposure to various pollutants in different urban and rural settings. The findings

from this investigation are expected to contribute significantly to the formulation of targeted public health policies and interventions aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of air pollution on human health.

5.4 RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

ECMWF has been working for many years with relevant stakeholders on the subject of air pollution via CAMS. More recently, the European commission has mandated CAMS to develop the Copernicus Health Hub (CHH) which is a single-entry point for all the Copernicus information that is relevant for the health sector.

CAMS and the CHH are working with international institutes such as WMO-WHO via the ClimaHealth, European institutes as European Environment Agency (EEA) and the European Climate and Health Observatory (ECHO), Lancet Countdown Europe, ECDC. CAMS is also working at local/national level with for example Sante Public de France (France) and Space4Health (Germany) or also using another CAMS programme (National Collaboration Programme) that provide a direct link with the national air quality institute or university.

The interaction with the different stakeholders is done via:

- collaboration – e.g. the CAMS National Collaboration Programme that allows direct discussion at country level,
- Projects – e.g. the Copernicus Health Hub, that has direct interaction with the global health community,
- and a collection of requirements gathered via ECMWF user support.

5.5 INDICATORS AND METRICS

The overarching objective of this pilot study encompasses two primary aspects: 1. Assessing the usability of data from IoT sensors, and 2. Identifying the additional benefits derived from these innovative measurements. To address these questions, a variety of quantitative and qualitative methodologies will be employed, details of which are provided below.

5.5.1 USABILITY

The raw data from IoT sensors exhibit high variability and noise, necessitating statistical methods for signal smoothing. Furthermore, the measurement time series frequently encounter outliers, thus requiring both standardisation and outlier filtering. A significant challenge is the limited availability of representative reference measurements, contrasted with pronounced spatial-temporal gradients. Standardisation can be achieved using straightforward statistical methods tailored to individual stations. For outlier detection and filtering, leveraging other (reliable) observations to constrain the data is a viable strategy. Employing various AI/ML tools could also be an effective approach. The amended time series should be evaluated against reference measurements (e.g., from *in situ* observations) using statistical skill scores to verify their usability.

5.5.2 ADDITIONAL BENEFIT

A notable anticipated benefit of IoT sensor measurements is their extensive spatial-temporal coverage. This capability facilitates the generation of high-resolution maps for designated areas and other pertinent locations, offering preliminary insights into the distribution of air pollutants. These maps can be cross-referenced with model data (such as CAMS) to pinpoint pollution hotspots on a hyperlocal scale. Furthermore, this comparison with model data can uncover and potentially rectify the shortcomings of each dataset. In addition, the IoT data time series are invaluable for substantiating air quality models and enhancing the accuracy of their forecasts.

5.6 INFLUENCE OF EXTERNAL FACTORS

5.6.1 POLLUTION SOURCES

In regions like Benelux, agriculture is a significant source of air pollutants, such as ammonia from livestock and fertilisers. This contrasts with urban areas, where combustion processes from industry and traffic are predominant, emitting nitrogen oxides, particulate matter, and other pollutants.

Similarly, in the Po Valley, industrial emissions and vehicular traffic, particularly in cities like Milan and Turin, are major pollution sources. Industries there emit significant amounts of Nox and sulphur dioxide (SO₂), while vehicles contribute to Nox and particulate matter emissions. Additionally, the valley's agricultural activities also release ammonia and other chemical pollutants into the air.

These varied sources result in a complex mixture of aerosols and gases in the atmosphere, each with its distinct properties and health impacts. IoT sensors in these areas need to discern these differences, adapting their detection capabilities to the prevalent pollution types.

5.6.2 TOPOGRAPHY

The topography of a region can profoundly affect air pollution levels and patterns. A prime example is the Po Valley, where the Alps create a natural barrier that hinders air circulation, leading to the accumulation of pollutants in the valley. Such orographical constraints can exacerbate pollution from both local sources (like agriculture and traffic) and regional sources (such as industrial emissions), particularly in valley regions.

In opposition, the Benelux region, having a mostly flat topography, experiences different dynamics. The lack of natural barriers facilitates the dispersion and transport of pollutants, allowing particles from the agricultural fields to travel greater distances and reach densely populated cities. Thus, the topographical features of the Benelux region play a key role in the spread and impact of air pollution, particularly from agricultural sources.

5.6.3 SEASONAL VARIABILITY AND METEOROLOGICAL CONDITIONS

The impact of different pollution sources is further modulated by seasonal changes and weather conditions. For instance, the use of coal for heating in winter or the intensification of agricultural activities in certain seasons can lead to temporal peaks in specific pollutants. Additionally, meteorological factors like solar radiation influence chemical reactions in the atmosphere, notably the conversion of Nox to ozone, which is more pronounced in sunnier, warmer periods. Wind and rain also significantly alter pollution levels, with the wind supporting dispersion and transport, while rain contributes to the deposition of pollutants from the air.

5.7 METHODOLOGIES AND TOOLS

The approach under consideration encompasses a variety of analytical methods to potentially enhance the evaluation of IoT data. This may include the use of statistical scores and geostatistical interpolation techniques, which could be instrumental in identifying potential hotspots and approximating pollution levels on a local scale. Additionally, aggregating data across various timeframes and scales might offer a more expansive, albeit less precise, perspective on pollution trends.

To potentially improve the accuracy of IoT sensor data, the implementation of calibration and bias correction processes is being contemplated, possibly utilising meteorological inputs such as humidity and temperature. This step, while theoretical at this stage, could be crucial in adjusting for environmental factors that may impact sensor readings.

The development of an efficient ingestion infrastructure is also a key aspect of this approach, aiming to effectively manage the extensive data generated by IoT sensors. This infrastructure would need to facilitate real-time data capture, storage, and processing, and be scalable to accommodate an anticipated increase in data volume.

Furthermore, the downscaling of CAMS data is another aspect that might be incorporated to achieve more detailed spatial resolution. By refining this broader-scale data to a localised context and potentially integrating additional data sources, there is a possibility to enhance the spatial detail of air quality analysis, leading to a more nuanced understanding of air pollution and its impacts.

5.7.1 REMOTE SENSING

While satellite-based measurements of air pollutants are not highly sensitive to the near-surface air layers (i.e., the lowermost 100 metres), they do provide extensive spatial coverage, enabling the analysis of spatial patterns across Europe. Specifically, datasets derived from a combination of high-resolution satellite instruments, such as MODIS and VIIRS for aerosol and particulate matter measurement, or Sentinel-5P/TROPOMI for ozone and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), when integrated with high-resolution air quality models, can offer significant insights into the distribution of air pollutants, including at an urban scale.

The satellite instruments mentioned are in low Earth orbit, resulting in only 1-2 measurements per day at any given location in Europe. However, the upcoming launch of the Meteosat Third Generation Sounding Satellite (MTG-S) introduces the Sentinel-4 instrument, which will enable the monitoring of (semi-) diurnal cycles of various air pollutants levels (including NO₂ and ozone) over Europe.

5.7.2 CITIZEN SCIENCE

Measurements from CitSci projects such as Sensor.Community³⁰ are pivotal to our pilot study. They not only provide access to a vast dataset from low-cost sensors, ensuring comprehensive spatiotemporal coverage, but also involve ordinary citizens conducting measurements in their living environments. This approach enables the estimation of air pollutant concentrations in these (residential) areas, potentially enhancing our understanding of people's overall exposure to air pollutants, particularly in relation to their home and workplace environments.

However, these projects do present certain challenges. These include the potential for incorrect sensor installation or inadequate maintenance of instruments, often due to the average citizen's limited technical expertise. Our pilot study, therefore, seeks to mitigate these issues through the application of various statistical methods and machine learning tools.

5.7.3 IN SITU SENSORS

For validating measurements from low-cost sensors, *in situ* observations from ground-based reference air quality stations are crucial. In this regard, data from national environmental agencies or the European Environment Agency (EEA) are particularly valuable. These measurements are maintained and regularly calibrated by experts, which significantly reduces uncertainties compared to data from CitSci projects or satellite measurements.

5.7.4 SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA

The evaluation of socio-economic data has not been done at this stage of the project. If possible a preliminary evaluation will be done in the second phase of the project.

³⁰ <https://sensor.community/>

5.8 UPDATED PROBLEM AND SOLUTION STATEMENT

Based on the project findings to date, the following updated Problem and Solution Statements were generated for the Pilot 3 Case.

Updated Problem Statement

Modern society, particularly sectors like industry and transportation, produces high amounts of emissions that negatively impact air quality. Exposure to high concentrations of air pollutants, such as particulate matter smaller than 2.5 μm and 10 μm (PM2.5, PM10), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and ozone (O₃), can lead to various health issues, including respiratory diseases such as asthma, chronic bronchitis, and even lung cancer.

The European air Quality Directive regulates and aims to improve air quality. To verify and monitor actions from the government, there are specialised measurement stations equipped with fairly expensive sensors. While these stations provide high quality measurements, their limited spatial coverage is insufficient to create in-depth assessments for a local context due to the associated costs. Furthermore, current remote sensing technology is not capable of addressing this task effectively.

Air quality data from cost-effective IoT devices (crowdsourced) could supplement reference data and thus could provide greater spatial coverage at a lower cost. The integration of IoT data is promising but also challenging due to several factors such as availability, reliability and representativeness of data, different data formats, incomplete metadata, and missing interoperability.

The spatial coverage is crucial for policy makers, who often decide on actions on a regional/municipal level and thus require a solid data basis to see if actions are needed, to justify new actions or to monitor existing strategies.

Updated Solution Statement (in AD4GD)

One primary objective is to address the current limitations in the coverage of air quality measurement networks. Therefore, integrating as many *in situ* observations as possible is crucial. One of the main goals is to create a high quality data stream that feeds both current and future ECMWF tools. To achieve this, the intention is to create pipelines that analyse incoming data on reliability and representativeness with the purpose to evaluate the feasibility of low-cost sensors in the context of the ECMWF framework. Finally, this new data stream could complement the current data sources (e.g. satellite and ground-based reference sensors), to enrich current and future tools through improved spatial resolution.

5.9 END-USER TOOL DESCRIPTION

Since Pilot 3 will focus on creating a set of methods to evaluate IoT observations that will eventually lead to an automated data pipeline, there is no need for a graphical user interface. Ideally, the output of the pipeline will be included into the ECMWF ecosystem that already has a set of visualisations and tools that will be used.

This is why no User Journey from the perspective of an end-user could be generated. Pilot 3 developed a journey from the perspective of a researcher at ECMWF (see Appendix A1, Figure 40). Four Phases are identified: Decode, Filter, Aggregate, and Intercomparison. The goal is to identify if IoT observations on air quality are representative enough to be used in a model framework (e.g. within CAMS) and if it adds value for the forecast models.

Phase 1: Decode

The decoding phase is all about bringing the data into a usable format and harmonised state. This begins with investigating and identifying what data is about. Furthermore, units are converted to SI units, for example, temperature data is converted into Kelvin. If the dataset itself does not provide units, units from the metadata are attached to the values.

This phase assumes that there is a new data set that has to be analysed. The acquisition of the data is not further described because this might vary a lot based on the data source. In the case of the pilot, ECMWF will focus on data from Pollutrack, Purple Air and Sensor.Community. These data sources include information about air pollutants such as nitrogen oxides, ozone, and particulate matter of dimensions less than 10µm or 2.5µm (PM2.5 and PM10). The actual actions for decoding are mostly done in Python.

Phase 2: Filter

During the filter phase erroneous data points (e.g., spikes, outliers) are removed from the data set.

Phase 3: Aggregate

In the aggregation phase, data is put into different granularities, for example, aggregated on an hourly or daily basis. This is done in the ECMWF infrastructure.

Phase 4: Intercomparison

The Intercomparison phase is the main phase of the journey. Here, different statistical methods are used to evaluate if the dataset actually provides value. The main aspects that are evaluated are subscale variability, representativeness, uncertainty, consistency, homogeneity, and trends (drift). To do this, the IoT observations are compared to reference data for instance from ground-based measurement networks. Furthermore, digital terrain models (DTM) with high spatial resolution might be included into the intercomparison, to factor in information about air flow into the process. The intercomparison is also done on the ECMWF infrastructure. If the intercomparison concludes that the data has high quality and has additional benefits with respect to ground-based measurement networks, the data assimilation into CAMS could begin, but this is out of scope of AD4GD. Touchpoints: Pollutrack API (under negotiation), Purple Air API (paid version, under investigation), Sensor.Community API (open, but every slow), CAMS (open) Data: Air pollutants (PM2.5, PM10, Nox, Ozone), location of the measurement (in degree format), Timestamps (UTC), Digital Terrain Models (DTM, high resolution, for air flow analysis).

5.10 TECHNICAL COMPONENTS REQUIRED TO SUPPORT THE PILOT STUDY

The above analysis identified several technical components needed to support the workflows and data pipelines of the air quality pilot study. These are summarised in Figure 12, and labelled according to whether a solution already exists, needs to be adapted or must be developed within the AD4GD project. In the latter case, the diagram identifies the section of this report where any relevant development is documented.

Pilot 3: Air Quality

AD4GD

Figure 12: Air pollution pilot technical components.

6 TECHNICAL COMPONENTS – IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 COMPONENT 1 – AUTOMATED INGESTION OF DATA FROM DIVERSE LOW-COST SENSORS

In the early months of the project, we needed to assess the feasibility of harvesting and aggregating data from multiple types of low-cost air quality sensor platforms³¹, which publish their data in a range of formats and via different channels. Commercial manufacturers commonly offer data hosting, and dashboards with visualisation and analysis tools for a user's own sensor platforms (see examples in Figure 13) but options for data download vary from email requests for zip files to interactive web page requests for csv download. Participatory science networks such as PurpleAir and Sensor.Community collate and expose all participants' data for viewing and download, but vary in their approach: Purple Air offers limited free downloads and has a business model ultimately based on charging for contributors' data, while Sensor.Community offers an API to access recent data, and an File Transfer Protocol (FTP) archive for historic data under the Open Database (OdbL) 1.0 licence to which users consent when registering their sensor platform.

³¹ In accordance with SOSA and other data models, we refer to 'sensor platform' as a device which may contain one or many 'sensors' (e.g. particulate sensor, temperature sensor, noise sensor). Thus a personal air quality monitoring device or a measuring station will be referred to in this text as a 'sensor platform' even though it is more colloquially called a 'sensor'.

Figure 13: Examples of commercial dashboards hosting data for a user's own sensor fleet, from Plume Flow (left) and Earthsense Zephyr (right).

Some hosting/visualisation platforms already bring together data from different sensor and sensor platform types. Sensor.Community allows a range of different static sensor types to be directly registered, of which the vast majority are currently the AirRohr open source kit measuring temperature, humidity, PM2.5 and PM10. The OpenAQ initiative³² collates some air quality sensor platform data from a range of open air quality networks including European reference stations and CitSci projects. This data is presented in a harmonised and queryable format: (e.g. <https://docs.openaq.org/recipes/list-locations-in-a-specific-country-that-measure-pm25>). Nevertheless, there are gaps and overlaps in the data that is federated by these initiatives, and no easy options for contributing data from some commercial sensor platforms to a public repository. Most importantly, the available interfaces do not offer easy options for comparing time series from different devices (e.g. To assess consistency), and none of the aggregating platforms currently have a schema capable of dealing with mobile sensor platform data.

A prototype system was developed specifically for the project, @h carries out a daily harvesting to ingest data from three different types of air quality sensor platform, including one mobile personal device: the Plume Flow 2³³, EarthSense Zephyr³⁴ and Sensor.Community open source AirRohr kit³⁵. The data retrieval process is different for each sensor platform type, ranging from web scraping to csv download. Full details can be seen in the code repository and documentation at <https://github.com/AstonAirQuality>.

Data is currently aggregated into a PostGIS database. The database and ingestion code are currently hosted on AWS, but can be deployed on a range of platforms. Each sensor platform type is harvested using a bespoke component instance for that type, and a Factory Method design pattern has been employed to make addition of a new sensor platform type as easy as possible (see Figure 14). For the commercial sensor platform types tested up to now, opportunities for re-use of ingestor components have been relatively limited, since few publish data using open standards, and it usually involves the bespoke coding of an ingestor component to request data via email, trigger a download request or scrape it from a dashboard.

³² <https://registry.opendata.aws/openaq>

³³ <https://plumelabs.com/en/flow/>

³⁴ <https://www.earthsense.co.uk/zephyr>

³⁵ <https://sensor.community/en/sensors/airrohr/>

Figure 14: Each sensor platform type is represented by a concrete product built to handle its specific data access requirements. Instances of the concrete product are instantiated by a factory class managed by a central wrapper client, which passes on specific parameters (e.g. sensor ID or authentication details) required to retrieve data for that concrete instance.

The system is currently ingesting and harmonising data from 8 Plume Flow 2 mobile sensors, 2 EarthSense Zephyrs and 2 Sensor.Community AirRohrs. Zephyrs and AirRohrs are registered to static locations, but the Flow data includes a dynamic series of observation coordinates which are used to calculate daily bounding boxes for spatial data indexing. Currently, the data history stretches back for 11 months (1149 database rows, corresponding to over 1.4 million individual observations). Historic data is compressed to a json BLOB which allows the storage of one row per day, but makes dynamic querying slower (see <https://github.com/AstonAirQuality> for further details). This data harvesting work allowed us to identify issues very early on in the project with field naming, data formatting and outliers, and to test some harmonisation and resampling strategies (see examples of file format variability in Figure 15).

```

|sensor_id;sensor_type;location;lat;lon;timestamp;P1;durP1;ratioP1;
P2;durP2;ratioP2
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:00:42;4.35;;;2.42;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:03:08;3.28;;;2.22;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:05:34;3.55;;;2.20;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:08:01;3.88;;;2.10;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:10:29;7.45;;;2.00;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:12:58;4.18;;;1.90;;

|timestamp,date,latitude,longitude|timestamp,"date (UTC)","NO2 (ppb)","VOC (ppb)","pm 10
1621846710,"2021-05-24 08:58:30",52.240204,-1.770364|(ug/m3)","pm 2.5 (ug/m3)","NO2 (Plume AQI)","VOC (Plume AQI)","pm
1621849406,"2021-05-24 09:43:26",52.240206,-1.770364|10 (Plume AQI)","pm 2.5 (Plume AQI)","pm 1 (ug/m3)","pm 1 (Plume
1621849782,"2021-05-24 09:49:42",52.240206,-1.770365|AQI)"
1621850230,"2021-05-24 09:57:10",52.240207,-1.770366|1621846700,"2021-05-24
1621850536,"2021-05-24 10:02:16",52.240207,-1.770366|08:58:20",0,61,144.59767,17.518475,0,5,140,35,8,21
1621850836,"2021-05-24 10:07:16",52.240209,-1.770368|1621846760,"2021-05-24
1621851149,"2021-05-24 10:12:29",52.240209,-1.770368|08:59:20",2,52,33.28648,5.523699,2,4,33,11,5,11
1621851503,"2021-05-24 10:18:23",52.240208,-1.77036

|Timestamp(UTC),Timestamp(UTS),Timestamp(Local),814-Temp(C)-slotB,814-Humidity(%RH)-
slotB,814-NO2(ug/m3)-slotB,814-O3(ug/m3)-slotB,814-NO(ug/m3)-slotB,814-PM10(ug/m3)-
slotB,814-PM2.5(ug/m3)-slotB,814-PM10(ug/m3)-slotB,814-Ambient temp(C)-slotB,814-Ambient
humidity(%RH)-slotB,814-Ambient pressure(hPa)-slotB
"2023-06-26T19:15:00+00:00",1687806900,"2023-06-
26T20:15:00+0100",30.1,30.36,10.59,0,0,0,2.75,3.03,29.9,30.57,1005.3
"2023-06-26T19:30:00+00:00",1687807800,"2023-06-
26T20:30:00+0100" 30.00 30.41 10.71 0.0 0.2 75.3 02.70 04.30 50.1005.5

```

Figure 15: Examples of the raw data format from three different sensor platforms: Sensor Community AirRohr (top), Plume Flow (centre – NB, this has two separate files for locations and measurements) and Earthsense Zephyr (bottom). This illustrates the variation in field names for the same phenomena across sensor platforms.

The ingestion prototype allows us to access data from sensor types not available through OpenAQ (e.g. mobile personal devices), and has also facilitated the easy intercomparison of data from experimentally collocated sensors, to evaluate quality and consistency (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Intercomparison of pairs of collocated sensors, showing non-systematic discrepancies (left) and systematic bias (right).

Within the prototype database, field names are harmonised at the ingestion stage using simple lookup tables. These are used in an analogous way to the more sophisticated field mappings used in the development of components Sections 6.3, 6.4, and 6.5, and have contributed to their development, (e.g. <https://github.com/avillar/ad4gd-semantics/blob/main/sensors-uplift.yml#L8>). We used the system to retrieve raw csv time series for testing at the internal project hackathon in October 2023 and in experiments carried out since.

We will continue to ingest data from the registered sensor platforms in order to provide an easy stream of testing data for the semantic enrichment components. We will add additional sensors to the ingestion pipeline, and will also add additional sensor platform types. This prototype was not intended as a long-term solution for retrieving sensor data, but has in fact proved to be very useful in facilitating experiments with semantic mapping and republishing. Currently, the open codebase allows a user to set up their own ingestion pipeline and database for any combination of these three specific sensor platform types. The github codebase will remain open for contribution of new sensor platform retrieval components, and some elements of the system may be re-used for ingesting sensor data in the other pilot studies.

6.2 COMPONENT 2 – EVALUATION OF CONNECTOR SOLUTIONS

Certain data providers who may be interested in joining the GDDS will want to have full control over their data, e.g., to decide who they share their data with, how much data they share, or monitor for which purposes their data is acquired. Data spaces by design should provide facilities to track and monitor data transactions, and implement policies that prevent data exploitation. Therefore, the GDDS will need to facilitate contractual data exchange where both data providers and data consumers can trust the infrastructure to support secure data transactions.

Dataspace connectors present a good candidate implementation to support the GDDS data exchange requirements. By definition, connectors facilitate secure and effective Data Exchange Services in data spaces and support common governance models and data sovereignty by design (Giussani and Steinbuss, 2023). Connectors provide APIs to data space participants to ensure interoperability. They offer identity management, communication security, and usage control. Connectors additionally act as trustworthy components and implement policy enforcement mechanisms for cybersecurity.

There is a growing number of dataspace connector projects emerging that offer code templates or graphical user interfaces to support developers in building custom dataspace connectors. Peter Koen (a co-chair of the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) working groups) however argues that “*We saw an entire zoo*

of different connectors and connector projects emerge. And these projects were partially not interoperable with each other within the same data space.” (Koen, 2023).

In this project, we considered two dataspace connector frameworks – the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) and the International Data Spaces (IDS) implementation – as potential candidates for the GDSS. The EDC implementation was selected for further testing over the IDS implementation, since IDS is no longer supported and it can only be used with pre-packaged datasets.

An EDC connector is a compiled Java (jar) file. Authentication from user to connector is done by an API key. There is no GUI to set the parameters but it can be developed as a separate component. Contract is negotiated between two connectors on the provider and a consumer side, but security and trust lead to overhead.

While EDC offers example connector implementations, bespoke provider-side and consumer-side connectors need to be programmed for each data provider (e.g., two connectors to serve and retrieve Rasdaman data). To test the EDC implementation, initial setup including two connectors for a simple transaction was deployed. This covers the simplest possible scenario in which a data provider is capable of creating an asset, establishing policies for it to be negotiated, as well as a data consumer able to actually negotiate a contract and request data from the provider. However, lack of developer documentation and technical support prevented successful deployment of test connector implementations.

At this stage, data connectors should be considered immature to be implemented in AD4GD due to the limited software development resources we have. The most reliable and meaningful way to implement the ‘Trust’-related functionalities, supposed to be implemented by connectors, is an OGC service that will support authentication or authorization based on a set of rules that acts as pre-sign contracts.

6.3 COMPONENT 3 – SEMANTIC UPLIFT: SPARQL/JSON-LD FOR DATA EXCHANGE

There is a growing amount of data available relevant to the Green Deal, but typically generated or produced by different systems and platforms, which are coming in most cases from different technology providers. As a result, data is usually available by different sources, in different formats, and represented according to different models, thereby hampering data integration and exchange across multiple solutions. The lack of integrated data access and interoperability, in turn, hinders the full potential of value creation based on all data available, and the development of smart services and applications supporting the decision making processes.

Linked Data and semantic technologies can be used to foster interoperability, by harmonising and providing context and meaning to metadata across different systems and domains. The backbone of Linked Data is RDF (Resource Description Framework)³⁶, a family of W3C specifications to describe all types of resources (which can be real things, abstract concepts, documents...). RDF descriptions are machine readable, and provide a shared context so that their meaning can be interpreted by computers and humans. Semantic technologies can be used to query data in RDF format, even from different repositories at once (via federation).

To be able to aggregate data acquired from different sources, a data user first needs to be certain of what this data contains. Ideally, data fields should be labelled consistently between different data providers, sensors, platforms, etc., but in practice, field names are generally inconsistent and in some cases ambiguous. For instance, in the air quality domain, particulate matter 10 (PM10) is labelled as *[sensor_ID]-PM10(ug/m3)-slotB* in Zephyr datasets, *pm 10 (ug/m3)* in Plume datasets, *pm 10.0_atm* in PurpleAir datasets, and *P1* in Sensor.Community datasets. For human users it might be challenging to understand the meaning of some of these fields, e.g., P1 is likely to be interpreted as particulate matter 1 (PM1), for machines, it is not possible to interpret these field names without additional semantic information. This example demonstrates how data aggregation (and automation of this process) depends on semantic interoperability – the ability of machines to exchange data with unambiguous meaning.

³⁶ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

In order to address the semantic interoperability challenges, we need an agreed common information model, or *lingua franca*, defining the data elements relevant to our domain(s) along with their associated semantics/meaning for information exchange. We also need to ensure the delivery of the necessary harmonisation mechanisms facilitating the integration of data coming from different sources, and standard interfaces for data access and exchange. Such a model typically comes in the form of an ontology (format specification of a shared conceptualization of a domain/application).

Interoperability can be addressed at different levels, from the technical (connectivity) aspects to the syntactic (formats) and the semantic (data models) aspects, and up to the organisation and legal aspects. Our focus in AD4GD is on the semantic interoperability aspects which require also the technical and syntactic elements in place.

At present, there is no integrated solution that can support the Green Deal semantic harmonisation, therefore in this project we will work towards a common Green Deal Information Model (GDIM) that will act as a common vocabulary to provide the basis of a common green deal data space, enabling interoperability and integration of different systems, potentially from different vendors. Our approach will involve both reusing existing components and ontologies and developing new code and introducing new domain-specific vocabularies.

The Agriculture Information Model (AIM) was developed in a previous project called DEMETER³⁷, and is currently under OGC standardisation (for more details, see D1.3, Section 3.2). The most important feature of the AIM was the architecture, which allowed it to be specialised/extended to different domains. The GDIM implemented in this project will reuse and build partially over the AIM. The model is publicly available in the AD4GD GitHub repository: <https://github.com/AD4GD/GDIM>.

The GDIM will be designed following a layered and modular approach and have the following layers (details in D1.3, Section 3.2): meta-model layer; cross-domain layer; domain layer; pilot-specific layer; metadata model layer. Of particular interest are the domain and pilot-specific layers that enable the integration of relevant vocabularies (e.g., vocabularies that can support the air quality data example described above).

Relevant domain and pilot-specific vocabularies will be continuously identified and integrated into the GDIM, accessible via the RAINBOW server triple store (see Section 6.12), which stores and exposes semantic triples³⁸ for querying. Unlike relational databases that store data as tables, triple stores store data as statements in the subject-predicate-object form. The RDF model described at the beginning of this section is a graph-based data model and framework for representing such triples, and is widely used for describing data in a semantically-enriched or annotated format.

The RDF model can be implemented in different RDF serialisation formats, including JSON-LD³⁹ (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data), which allows representation of semantically-enriched data in a developer-friendly manner and in alignment with the common way of services exposing data (JSON). Using RDF or JSON-LD also allows to validate that the data is compliant with the common data model (e.g., GDIM) not only in its structure, but also that it conforms to semantic constraints (e.g., the value of a unit of measurement for a particular observation should be x or y).

Our information model in AD4GD is formally specified in an ontology, but we generate from it a JSON-LD context which can then be used by the services/applications to exchange data with semantic meanings attached. Semantic enrichment (lifting) of data is performed via data transformation, e.g., original data in CSV format is transformed to RDF, stored in RDF triplestore, and is accessible using SPARQL⁴⁰ endpoint. Alternatively we can create a virtual semantic layer, which does query translation. The data stays in the

³⁷ See: https://h2020-demeter.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/DEMETER_D21_final.pdf

³⁸ A triple is a sequence of three entities that represents a statement in the form of subject–predicate–object expressions (e.g., "sds011_1 measures PM10_mcg_m3", "PM10_mcg_m3 has units mcg_m3") (<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/#section-triples>)

³⁹ JSON-LD is a method of encoding (serialising) linked data (e.g., RDF triples) using JSON (<https://json-ld.org/>).

⁴⁰ SPARQL is a semantic query language designed to retrieve and manipulate data stored in RDF format.

original source (e.g., relational database, JSON/CSV from REST API) and we generate semantic data dynamically that can be accessed via a SPARQL endpoint. In this case, no physical RDF data is generated.

The STA service created for the AD4GD project (<https://sta-sta.apps.paas-dev.psnc.pl/>) creates on the fly an STA endpoint on top of a SPARQL endpoint that exposes data according to the SOSA/SSN⁴¹ ontology (part of the GDIM). So, data can be physically in any form as long as it can be queried via SPARQL and modelled according to the SOSA/SSN standard.

Initial testing of the GDMI and AD4GD Data Preparation and Integration (DPI) pipelines (for more details on DPI see D1.3, Section 4.2.1) was conducted for Pilots 1 and 3. For Pilot 1, sample data from the Berlin Senate Wasserportal was transformed into GDIM-compliant format using SPARQL. The dataset consisted of monthly mean water levels from 21.12.2013 (including monthly minimum and maximum values). The mappings file that transforms CSV to RDF is publicly available from AD4GD GitHub at: <https://github.com/AD4GD/GDIM/tree/main/AD4GD-pilots-mappings/wasserstand>. Figure 15 shows representation of the water level dataset in GDIM. More details on the transformation are provided in D1.31, Section 3.4.

Figure 17: Representation of CSV data from the Berlin Senate “Wasserportal” in GDIM (the terms in orange are not yet part of the GDIM and will be added to the pilot extension module) (figure taken from D1.3, Section 3.4).

For Pilot 3, a sample air quality dataset from Sensor.Community was transformed into GDIM-compliant format using SPARQL and exposed in STA format. The sample dataset consisted of 1 day of measurements (01.04.2023) collected by two air quality sensors SDS011 (measures PM2.5 and PM10) and BME280 (measures pressure, temperature and humidity) which are installed on same sensor platform (i.e., collocated).

The SPARQL mappings from CSV format to the GDIM for this datasets can be found on GitHub: <https://github.com/AD4GD/GDIM/tree/main/AD4GD-pilots-mappings/sensor-community>. Data in STA format can be accessed from:

<https://www.foodie-cloud.org/describe?url=http%3A%2F%2Fw3id.org%2Fad4gd%2Fairquality%2Fsensorcommunity%2Fprocedure%2Fsensing&sid=560>.

⁴¹ Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) ontology is an ontology for describing sensors and their observations. SOSA (Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator) is a core ontology of SSN that includes elementary classes and properties (<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>).

The GDIM will continue evolving and updated with domain and pilot-cases specific vocabularies. It is also planned to connect ATOS data collection pipelines for water data in Berlin to PSNC data harmonisation pipelines, so that semantically-enriched data can be automatically generated and made available via STA endpoint. At the end of the project, an agreed GDIM and finalised data transformation pipelines will be delivered together with the interfaces to visualise and consume the integrated data.

6.4 COMPONENT 4 – MOBILISING DATA TO STAPLUS

As already exemplified earlier in this section, many IoT data providers offer their data in a non-standardised format (e.g., CSV files) that needs to be transformed and semantically-enriched to become interoperable. Data producers and providers might actually be willing to offer their data in an interoperable form, but might lack technical knowledge and resources to transform their data. On the other hand, data consumers might find it challenging to construct valid STA queries and navigate complex STA data structures to retrieve required data.

While STA/STApplus standards are well-documented and there is FROST server implementation for STA and a FROST server plugin to support STApplus extension, expert knowledge is required to serve and request IoT data in STA format. This calls for a tool or a set of tools that can offer intuitive and user-friendly interfaces to interact with STA/STApplus services.

TAPIS (Tables from APIs for Sensors) is a client application developed in HTML and Javascript to support data mobilisation to STApplus. The tool is inspired by Orange Data Mining toolkit⁴² that provides a user friendly drag-and-drop visual interface. TAPIS allows semantic annotation of data tables and facilitates a mapping from tables to the STA data model. Key functionality is summarised below; more details can be found in deliverable D1.3, Section 4.2.3.

The tool depends on the existence of a STApplus service (e.g., FROST server) and can work with any STApplus instance. Using TAPIS, CSV tables can be imported into an STApplus server automatically. This is achieved by loading a CSV file and mapping the data fields to STA classes and properties using GUI (see Figure 18).

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Upload table as STA observations". It contains two radio buttons: "Each row represents a feature of interest with several observed properties" (selected) and "Several observed properties of the same feature in a single column and in multiple rows". Below the radio buttons is a "Position:" section with three dropdown menus: "Place description" (set to "place"), "Longitude" (set to "long"), and "Latitude" (set to "lat"). There is also a "Date and time:" dropdown menu set to "phenomenonTime". At the bottom, there is a text input field for "STA service URL" containing "https://citiobs.demo.secure-dimensions.de/stapplus/v1.1" and an "Upload" button.

Figure 18: Upload table as STA observations from TAPIS STA+ reader (submit) (taken from D1.3).

To retrieve data, the client constructs and sends requests to the STApplus server and the responses are received in JSON but transformed into tables. The resulting tables can also be represented as graphs (time series) or exported to other formats including GeoJSON (see Figure 19).

⁴² <https://orangedatamining.com/>

Figure 19: TAPIS STApplus reader – exporting a dataset into a GeoJSON file (taken from D1.3).

Using TAPIS, CSV tables can be semantically enriched by generating CSVW⁴³ files. Figure 20, Figure 21 and Figure 22 illustrate an example of loading a water availability CSV table into TAPIS, adding appropriate fields' descriptions (semantic meaning) to two data fields, and exporting a CSVW file.

Figure 20: Importing CSV table into TAPIS to convert it into CSVW format.

⁴³ CSVW (CSV on the Web) is a standard for describing and clarifying the content of tabular data (e.g., cells, rows and columns).

Figure 21: Adding semantic meaning to CSV table using TAPIS.

Figure 22: Saving CSV table as CSVW file using TAPIS.

The resulting CSVW mappings generated by TAPIS for two data fields are shown below. As can be seen, the “Datum” CSV column is now mapped to the “phenomenonTime” and the “Tagesmittelwert” column is mapped to “Lake level”.

```
{
  "tableSchema": {
    "columns": [
      {
        "name": "Datum",
        "datatype": "string",
        "titles": "phenomenonTime",
        "propertyUrl": "http://www.opengis.net/def/docs/15-078r6/Observation/phenomenonTime"
      },
      {
        "name": "Tagesmittelwert",
        "datatype": "string",
        "titles": "Lake level",
        "propertyUrl": "https://hydro.geodab.eu/hydro-ontology/concept/15",
        "unitMeasureTitles": "Centimeters",
        "unitMeasureSymbol": "cm",
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```

        "unitMeasureUri": "https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/CentiM"
    }
}
},
"dialect": {
    "header": true,
    "delimiter": ";"
}
}

```

TAPIS implementation is capable of requesting records incrementally even if the server implementation is limited to 1000 records. Initial testing indicates a limit of 100000 records because the application runs in a web browser and there are memory limitations on JavaScript. The tool is available at: <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat/>. Open source code can be downloaded from GitHub: <https://github.com/joanma747/TAPIS>.

In due course, more functionalities will be implemented such as STA \$filter or \$expand. Additionally, new table operations and more export formats will be added.

TAPIS will also be used to test transformation of GBIF species occurrences data to STAplus format. GBIF provides a RESTful API as a programmatic way to publish and query data on GBIF.org, returning results in csv or JSON format. However, the GBIF API⁴⁴ does not follow OGC standards, thus making it difficult to automatically integrate the data in the context of the Green Deal Data Space. One approach is to transform GBIF CSV data into STAplus format while preserving DOIs to comply with GBIF data licence and citation conditions⁴⁵. This allows us to apply a meaning infrastructure on top of the data, to add additional semantic meaning to the values. The TAPIS approach will therefore be tested within pilot 2 as a means for transforming GBIF occurrence data to STAplus while maintaining the DOIs and provenance information of the data.

6.5 COMPONENT 5 – MOBILISING SENSOR DATA WITH STA

An ever-increasing quantity of IoT sensor data is becoming available in different domains. For AD4GD pilot cases such data may include air quality measurements coming from different types of sensors published by a variety of data providers, water quality and water availability data, weather data, images from camera trap sensors. Publication and integration of such heterogeneous types of IoT data presents a major challenge and requires a standardised data model such as OGC STA/STAplus.

Figure 23 (also included in the deliverable D3.1) depicts current IoT server infrastructure deployed by IoT Labs. The components include the FROST server⁴⁶ (compliant to STAplus model using a plugin), the FIWARE (Future Internet-Ware) context brokers and TM Forum IoT server. NGINX will act as a data harmonisation layer to convert FIWARE or TM Forum data to STAplus data. The FROST server is composed of two main endpoints: <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthingsapi/> (OGC SensorThings API) and <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/> (permits the user to handle the requests to the FROST server directly through a GUI). Detailed description of the infrastructure is offered in deliverable D3.1, Section 6.

⁴⁴ <https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.gbif.org/citation-guidelines>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/FraunhoferIOSB/FROST-Server>

Figure 23: IoT Lab servers installation (taken from D3.1).

The IoT lab infrastructure was used to carry out initial testing to transform water quality and water level CSV data to STApplus format. Sample data used consisted of two water level datasets for Plötzensee lake and a water quality dataset for river Spree, both obtained from the authorities from Berlin. Detailed description of the data transformation is provided in the deliverable D3.1, Sections 9 and 12. Harmonised sample data can be accessed from <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things>. In due course, more IoT data will be transformed and added to FROST server from three pilots, including live data streams.

In terms of planned future development, IoT Labs will focus on implementing a multi-protocol parser as a service. This multi-protocol parser will receive data in a given IoT communication protocol and convert the data to other IoT communication protocols. For instance, data coming from an IoT device using the FIWARE NGSI-LD data format will be converted into STApplus format. The different IoT servers (FROST/STA, FIWARE context brokers and TM Forum IoT) will be used to store the converted data.

6.6 COMPONENT 6 – DATA CUBES FOR CONSUMING, PUBLISHING AND PROCESSING MULTIDIMENSIONAL DATA

Environmental problems tend to be complex and multifactorial and so require multidimensional analytical capabilities to properly understand and monitor them. One of the GDDS technological challenges, therefore, is to combine multidimensional layers (e.g. raster or vector maps) coming from various sources in a single managed infrastructure to deploy these complex analytical queries, taking account of authentication and access rights for every type of user. For users, it is challenging to find and combine multiple thematic datasets with rich metadata for a user-selected area, possibly over a customised time interval. For data producers (including the workflows of the AD4GD case studies), we need a way to organise and publish logically related data layers (e.g. time series of spatial data) and group them by topic with the same documentation on methodology and licensing so that they can be discovered, queried and used together.

The main issues are related to handling different scales, dimensions and formats (raster-oriented, point-oriented like observations, grid-recorded etc.) in the same data cube.

Data cube technology is being developed on various platforms (Open Data Cube⁴⁷, Rasdaman⁴⁸, FAIRiCube⁴⁹, Data Cubes with STAC⁵⁰, THREDDS⁵¹ and consuming and supplying usage and processing of NetCDF, NetCDF4, Cloud Optimized Geotiff, Zarr, GRIB data). ECMWF makes heavy use of data cubes to represent forecast model outputs, typically in GRIB format. As such it has extensive infrastructure and software dedicated to the task of storing, archiving, converting, and retrieving GRIB/netCDF4 encoded datacubes. Some of this infrastructure is being reused and adapted to serve the needs of the AD4GD project, notably the Fields DataBase (FDB)⁵². Work is ongoing to integrate these tools with the approaches to open standards, metadata and semantic interoperability that exist within the project.

Observational data from weather stations and IoT data, widely used in Pilot 3, do not fit the typical definition of a datacube and are typically stored in a tabular format. However this data can be interpreted as a kind of sparse data cube and, as such, operations defined on data cubes can still be performed on it. Within ECMWF, such data is typically represented in a format called ODB, which is a compressed tabular format. ECMWF software such as the FDB is capable of handling and performing queries over data encoded in ODB format. Experiments are ongoing within Pilot 3 and WP4 to determine how best to adapt these formats and software to serve the needs of the GDDS.

To combine the achievements of various tools, platforms, and formats to store multidimensional data, the GeoDataCube Standards Working group is improving interoperability between them⁵³ to access and process data through a new API defining exchange format recommendations, profiles, and a metadata model.

In AD4GD we propose the use of Data Cubes to solve the multifactorial issues of FLC (Pilot 2). Our approach is focused on consuming and publishing multidimensional data on connectivity and other variables (bioclimatic, landscape indicators, socioeconomic data, etc.), reusing Open Data Cube. Meanwhile, other approaches which would supply Open Data Cube implementation, including semantic enrichment of remote sensing data, are planned to be implemented (see below).

For the Pilot 2, Open Data Cube is implemented through a series of steps:

- Connecting to the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>) to retrieve raw Sentinel images. This is done through automatic queries to the API for browsing and downloading (see Example 1, Example 2)
- The obtained images are transformed from the original SAFE format into OGC Cloud Geotiff to ingest these images directly to the Open Data Cube. The time series goes from 2018 to the present.
- From the Sentinel 2 images, LULC maps for 8 periods of time (1987, 1992, 1997, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017, 2022) are obtained and uploaded to the Open Data Cube.
- From the LULC maps, Terrestrial Connectivity maps based on cover frictions are computed which are also uploaded to the Open Data Cube.

The basic structure of the Open Data Cube has been created through a database which is running under PgAdmin and can be accessed/queried through Jupyter Lab. 7889 Sentinel 2 images have been downloaded and transformed into OGC COG. The process of metadata documentation and ingestion to the Open Data Cube is still ongoing.

⁴⁷ Open Data Cube. <https://www.opendatacube.org/>

⁴⁸ Rasdaman. <https://rasdaman.org/>

⁴⁹ FAIRiCUBE. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059238>

⁵⁰ Data Cubes with STAC.

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/earthdatalogin/vignettes/gdalcubes-stac-cog.html>

⁵¹ THREDDS. <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/tds/>

⁵² Fields DataBase. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3093172.3093238>

⁵³ GeoDataCube Standards Working group.

<https://www.ogc.org/press-release/ogc-forms-new-geodatacube-standards-working-group/>

The ICT maps, deriving from MiraMon, have also been ingested to the Open Data Cube for the complete time series and considering every thematic category as a possible dimension on the cube: Aquatic environments, Forests, Shrublands, Herbaceous crops, and Woody crops (Figure 24). The process of metadata documentation and ingestion of the LULC is still ongoing.

As said, the database behind the Open Data Cube which contains the arrays for every layer, can be accessed through JupyterLab⁵⁴. This method, though, doesn't allow for a proper control of users' access rights, authentication and trustable exchange of information, which is one of the main challenges of the Data Spaces. To this end, a CGI client is being developed to access and retrieve data from the Data Cube using the OGC WCS making this solution fully standard and FAIR-aligned.

Figure 24: Instance of connectivity maps outputs in Open Data Cube obtained through a query in the JupyterLab.

The next steps for planned development are as follows:

- An OGC WMS/WCS browser will be deployed to run on top of the Data Cube, in order to be able to visually reflect the results of queries and multidimensional analysis. Currently, the only possible way to compute and visualise data is JupyterLab.
- To deploy a range of other raster data on Open Data Cube (bioclimatic variables, including temperature, precipitation, tree canopy cover, and socioeconomic data, according to the vocabularies of GEO Essential Variables) to cover variables of species distribution models and connectivity to predict, and to ingest them into the Open Data Cube.

⁵⁴ An instance of query to the datacube to retrieve a Sentinel-2 image. [https://www.datacube.cat/cgi-bin/mmdc.py?SERVICE=WCS&VERSION=2.0.1&REQUEST=GetCoverage&SUBSET=E\(42240147,43740147\)&SUBSET=N\(45,82942.45,4590742.45\)&COVERAGEID=s2_level2a_utm31_10&FORMAT=image/jpeg&RANGESUBSET=red&SUBSET=ansi\(%222023-07-01%22\)](https://www.datacube.cat/cgi-bin/mmdc.py?SERVICE=WCS&VERSION=2.0.1&REQUEST=GetCoverage&SUBSET=E(42240147,43740147)&SUBSET=N(45,82942.45,4590742.45)&COVERAGEID=s2_level2a_utm31_10&FORMAT=image/jpeg&RANGESUBSET=red&SUBSET=ansi(%222023-07-01%22))

An instance of query to the datacube to retrieve an ICT map derived from MiraMon (2017).

[https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py?SERVICE=WCS&VERSION=2.0.1&REQUEST=GetCoverage&SUBSET=E\(260145,527685\)&SUBSET=N\(4488645,4747995\)&COVERAGEID=TerrestrialConnectivityIndex&FORMAT=image/tiff&RANGESUBSET=Forest&SUBSET=ansi\(%222017-01-01%22\)](https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py?SERVICE=WCS&VERSION=2.0.1&REQUEST=GetCoverage&SUBSET=E(260145,527685)&SUBSET=N(4488645,4747995)&COVERAGEID=TerrestrialConnectivityIndex&FORMAT=image/tiff&RANGESUBSET=Forest&SUBSET=ansi(%222017-01-01%22))

- To incorporate GBIF occurrences data through the connection with Horizon B3⁵⁵ project (HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-17, n° 101059592) datacubes. In particular, “D2.1 Software specifications”⁵⁶ will be analysed to perform the integration between their Species occurrence cube and the AD4GD Pilot2 DataCube.
- To encode GBIF occurrence data in OGC standard STApplus to show interoperability among different systems, in particular, connect them as single observations (not per pixel) into the WMS/WCS browser running on top of the DataCube.
- To implement processing/analytical steps in data cubes as an experimental tool to process raw input LULC data.

At the end of the AD4GD project, we aim for a reliable and swift solution to publish, access and consume input raster data and additional variables from multi-source servers for a user’s purposes, including an example implementation involving computations of terrestrial habitat connectivity (see Section 6.7) on the processing platform outside of data cubes, through the optimised deployment of raster data inside data cubes.

6.7 COMPONENT 7 – OPEN WORKFLOWS FOR HABITAT CONNECTIVITY COMPUTATION

Pilot 2 requires us to produce an open and re-usable workflow by which users can:

- run FLC computations smoothly and quickly, based on user-chosen values and parameters;
- refine and enrich input raster LULC data with other data on connectivity barriers, both human-made (roads and railways) and natural ones (waterways).

The components of this processing workflow are deployed as docker images to keep the analysis environment consistent, and to allow workflow modules to be run either as an open-source service (as envisaged to support the BioConn client) or on a user’s own machine.

A wide variety of tools exist for computing FLC, designed mostly by academic researchers (e.g. Graphab, Conefor, MiraMon plugin for terrestrial connectivity, Circuitscape, Linkage Mapper). Plenty of open-source geospatial tools also exist to support the necessary preprocessing of vector and raster data (e.g. gdal, SAGA, GRASS or QGIS packages) with specific pros and cons in accuracy, formats consumed, computing time and ease of installation exist. However, these are generally downloaded and used locally, and a reproducible open workflow for carrying out FLC analysis is not currently available. Our approach is focused on re-use of existing tools – Graphab and MiraMon plugin to compute terrestrial connectivity for each patch of habitats (see the detailed description of software and metrics used in Section 4.6). Meanwhile, it requires additional modifications of both tools – development of the Graphab’s looping mode to consume flexible variables and input LULC datasets and impedance maps, and transformation of MiraMon plugin into a standalone tool for computing ICT not based on batch processes (currently developing). Therefore, both re-use and development of new code are involved in this technical component.

The preprocessing step is mostly focused on the development of new Python code but based on existing libraries (osgeo, gdal, numpy, geopandas, 67onne, etc.) through a docker deployment to ensure consistency of environment and to allow the workflow to be run reliably either on a user’s machine or as an open service module.

Graphab, Conefor and MiraMon connectivity computation tools are open-access self-contained applications based on different mathematical approaches (graph and pixel-by-pixel computations respectively). Raster LULC data are the crucial cornerstones in both approaches, other input data, including vector and

⁵⁵ <https://b-cubed.eu/data-and-evidence>

⁵⁶ https://b-cubed.eu/storage/app/uploads/public/64d/1f7/5a2/64d1f75a2fc96997998232.pdf#file_name=D2.1_2023_Software_specifications.pdf

text/numerical ones specified by the user may vary. MiraMon computations are one-step only, while Graphab computations are multi-step and more flexible, providing plenty of optional outputs (for details see Section 4.4).

Graphab can run on any machine with a Java Runtime Environment (JRE), but depends on the HPC cluster to enhance performance. The MiraMon plugin is written in C and doesn't depend on extra libraries and plugins, but is currently restricted to Windows environments.

Both Graphab and Conefor are relatively simple to use and install on any user machines with widely-used operating systems, the computation of connectivity indices requires considerable amount of time and GPU even for local case study areas (Foltête et al. 2012a). Therefore, it becomes mandatory to proceed with these computations through a High-Performance Computing (HPC) mode. Parallel computing is crucial to supply users with quick computations and give them opportunity to upload new data, for instance, LULC changes prompting the recalculation of the whole graph. Since Graphab provides more exhaustive documentation, a variety of additional options (for instance, adding transformations in land use) and it may be parallelised through the native MPI mode, Graphab has been chosen over Conefor to ensure a more reliable and fast implementation of graph theory software.

The nested preprocessing workflow which has been developed updates the original LULC raster data using vector data from user-specified or OSM datasets to make output data more accurate and to describe barriers between habitats correctly (Figure 25). This workflow is highly dependent on other libraries (see above), but some of them are replaceable – for example, simple buffering may be executed using a range of libraries (e.g. gdal, qgis, grass, geopandas, shapely) with varying performance.

Figure 25: Nested workflow of pre-processing land-use/land-cover (LULC) data.

The sub-nested workflow to retrieve open-access OSM data through Nominatim API has been also devised (Figure 26). The workflow we have currently developed is dependent on the Nominatim API, but this may be replaced with Overpass API or Mapbox API if any execution issues on different processing platforms are revealed in future work. Overpass API and Nominatim API have both been tested to retrieve vector data from OSM for Catalonia (212 408 spatial features). From these tests we conclude that the Nominatim API provides an efficient solution to import linear and polygonal OSM data, which is stored as a single temporary geopackage file for the next steps of preprocessing.

Figure 26: Sub-nested workflow of preprocessing data from OSM.

The main limitations of OSM data for obtaining connectivity barriers stem from inconsistencies which are typical for a volunteered and relatively unstructured data source, namely:

- User mistakes in assigning text or numerical values, especially in areas remote from settlements (e.g., assigning values for 'level' key – e.g. intermittent waterway has been assigned with level = -1, while it must be ground level)
- Adding text values in a 'width' column, which requires the additional preprocessing step to reformat data.
- Abundance of NULL values for specific columns, mostly width and level, which requires to consider default values depending on other columns, for instance, road types – primary/secondary/tertiary/etc.
- A complex and bulky tagging system (e.g., the layer of water lines for case area retrieved initially is described by 123 keys, apart from id) which requires additional filtering steps.
- Inconsistency in assigning values for keys in specific cases (as an illustration, an overlap between 'intermittent' and 'seasonal' keys exists (Figure 27) due to discrepancy between user opinions and extending the set of keys as OSM develops).

Figure 27: Differences between keys 'intermittent' and 'seasonal' in OSM data.

Four compiled sources of LULC raster data (series of 8 maps, integer values from 1 to 25, 77694631 pixels per each map) have been merged based on well-established methodology (González-Guerrero, O., Pons, X., 2020) as Catalonian LULC data do not cover neighbouring regions and countries. Review of all connectivity indices, their representativeness and illustrativeness have been carried out (see Section 4.4) as technical implementation and performance are directly depend on the set of indices and their requirements to input data (for instance, time to compute local metrics may significantly vary depending on the level of math complexity).

Meanwhile, the native Graphab's MPI mode turned out to be an unreliable and complicated solution for resource-heavy computations, since sample commands in MPI-mode take more time than non-MPI commands on ECMWF virtual machines. Moreover, compression (from Geotiff to Cloud Optimised Geotiff (COG) with LZW compression) and data type transformations (from decimal values to int16 or int8) of input LULC data do not considerably reduce time to compute graph for case area and do not reduce the size of intermediate outputs in Graphab. To date, the computation of habitat corridors in Graphab for the entire Catalonia is strongly limited by machine capabilities (only computations with maximum distance = 250 m are not causing Java heap space errors) (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Corridors between forest patches (Graphab outputs).

However, computation performance has been significantly (6x times) increased through the Eagle HPC platform based on preliminary tests with a dockerised Graphab deployment⁵⁷. Sample Graphab commands which may be run through the command-line mode have been deployed on the Eagle HPC cluster developed by PSNC. Test computations have been run using the equivalent of docker configuration file and image for HPC, consisting of the singularity definition file (.def), container/image (.sif), and the job file (.sh). Compared to work machines belonging to Aston University, computation of elementary sample code in non-MPI mode on Eagle cluster is six times faster (00:40:11 and 00:06:41).

The final Graphab and MiraMon outputs representing habitat connectivity at each 5-year timestep from 1987 to 2022 have been published through MiraMon CGI as COG files to facilitate the access to output data. Even though Graphab can process state-of-the-art computations of FLC, its implementation should be supervised, accessed, and analysed by professionals. Graphab flexibility is one of the main disadvantages at the same time, for instance, default values of patch capacity might exaggerate the real importance of connectivity within the largest forest patches in Pyrenees (for further details see Appendix A4). It became obvious that comparing these results to Miramon outputs is not meaningful as it mostly depends on the capacity of habitat patches. Therefore, engagement with relevant stakeholders, including environmental consultants, is required to involve more expert knowledge.

Currently, the computation of ICT indices by the MiraMon module is developed as a long concatenation of batch processes with numerous instances. This process is also taking a significant amount of time and machine resources to read and store images as code is yet to be optimised as a stand-alone application.

As an example, the computation for just one pixel of 390 m, is the following:

```
:label1
rem Column:2 Row:0
c:\miramon\Retalla_64.exe 1 Impedancies\ImpedanciesForests.img
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\ImpedanciesForests_Retall 258765.00000 263475.00000
4745445.00000 4750155.00000 /ERR
FOR /F %%c in (result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\temp.txt) do set
var_SECCIO_a_ATTRIBUTE_DATA=%%c
IF %var_SECCIO_a_ATTRIBUTE_DATA% == -9999 type
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\temp.txt >> result_Forests_390_2355\ICT_final_1.txt
IF %var_SECCIO_a_ATTRIBUTE_DATA% == -9999 goto label2
c:\miramon\Retalla_64.exe 1 Afinities\AfinitiesForests.img
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\AfinitiesForests_Retall 258765.00000 263475.00000
4745445.00000 4750155.00000 /ERR
c:\miramon\CreaRas.exe result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\ImpedanciesForests_Retall.img
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Diana byte 0 1 x x /DESC_NODATA="Sense dades" /ERR
c:\miramon\ConvRel.exe 1 result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Diana.img /BACKUP /ERR
c:\miramon\VR.exe C 261120.00000 4747800.00000 1
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Diana x
c:\miramon\GenCost_64.exe 1 result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Diana.img
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\ImpedanciesForests_Retall.img
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Delta.img 0 /ERR /SAC /SIL
c:\miramon\CalcIMG.exe result_Forests_390_2355\Formula_ICT_1.mmc /ERR /SAC /SIL
c:\miramon\EstRas_64.exe 1 result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Calcul_ICT.img
result_Forests_390_2355\_$_ICT_temp_$_1\Sumatori_ICT.ini N /SUMAT /ERR /SAC /SIL
```

⁵⁷ Graphab deployment. <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2/tree/main/graphab>

The computation times for just one timestamp are the following:

	Aquatic environments	Forest	Herbaceous crops	Woody crops	Shrublands	Total
Time (hours)	59.52	11.83	23.80	14.55	19.72	129.42
Machine properties	Intel®Xeon® CPU X5675 @3.07GHz (2 processors) RAM 48.0Mb Windows Server 2012R2 x64	Intel®Core®i5-10500 CPU @3.10GHz 3.10 GHz 16.0 GB (15.8 GB usable) Windows 10 Enterprise x64	Intel® Xeon® CPU E5-2407 0 @ 2.20GHz 2.20 GHZ (2 processors) 32GB RAM Windows server 2012 R2 Standard x64	Intel® Xeon® CPU E5-2640 v4 @2.40GHz 2.40 GHz (2 processors) 128GB RAM Windows server 2012 R2 Standard x64	Intel® Xeon® CPU E5630 @2.53GHz 2.53GHz (2 processors) 8GB RAM Windows server 2012 R2 Standard x64	

The total time to execute all computations for 7 timescales amounts to 905.92 hours (37.75 days). To provide a swift computation tool for Pilot 2, we are currently developing a single stand-alone application which will be much more efficient in managing time and machine resources and it's expected to reduce computation times, thus allowing for connectivity computation in higher resolutions. This application will be also tested in other environments and operating systems through Wine and Docker.

Compared to connectivity computations, the initial version of preprocessing input LULC data and enriching them with vector data from other sources does not consume a significant amount of resources (for instance, 12:03:38 for the entire region of Catalonia) (for the further details see the first draft of preprocessing workflow on Github⁵⁸). The most bulky parts of code are dedicated to transformations from vector to raster.

At this stage, performance of the sub-nested workflow of retrieving relevant OSM data is estimated to be even better while looping through all the workflow steps compared to the other parts of the preprocessing workflow. The most time-consuming code parts are raster-vector transformations compared to retrieving data needed from OSM for Catalonia (00:08:37 on a machine with 10 cores CPU, 8 GB RAM).

The next steps are:

- To adopt preprocessing nested workflow to MiraMon plugin as it computes the negative “edge effect” of human infrastructure based on raw input data, whereas input data for Graphab (impedance raster files) should be pre-processed to reflect the real cost of migration through various LULC types.
- To deploy the developed standalone MiraMon tool on Docker to ensure the consistency of the environment.
- To deploy and test other Graphab commands on the Eagle HPC cluster with increasing complexity, including Graphab’s native MPI mode and allocation of a higher amount of memory to be consumed by Java, to increase the performance of Graphab commands.

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2/tree/main/preprocessing>

- To improve the performance of preprocessing code, consistently transforming it into the more generic workflow to be applied for any FLC case, not only for Catalonia and buffer for neighbouring countries and regions.
- To process existing auxiliary vector data from the several branches of Catalonian government (infrastructures, water bodies and waterways, protected areas for the recent period), to adopt existing tools to open-access (OSM) or user-uploaded data and use generic approach as much as it is possible.
- To devise a generic approach to record metadata from all steps of processing workflow in the comprehensive data provenance model and mapping outputs to relevant Essential Biodiversity Variable Products, enabling linking and cross-walking.
- To test ML models (together with ATOS) to predict future FLC based on existing LULC data, training the system and verifying it by LULC and connectivity data at previous timestamps (1987-2017).

By the end of the AD4GD project, we plan to deliver a generic semi-automatic workflow that allows any user to upload their own raster and vector LULC data or consume existing open-access data, including MUCSC or OSM, specify what parts of vector data should be used to rewrite input raster data, get the refined LULC data to process it further through Graphab/MiraMon software and obtain raster outputs containing values of various connectivity indices and statistics per types of habitats.

6.8 COMPONENT 8 – WATER MODELLING AND PREDICTION

Decision makers such as Members of the Berlin Senate or Berlin Districts Lake Managers need to make informed decisions to prioritise rehabilitation measures and resources to support lakes in Berlin. While historic and current data on water quality and water availability might be available for some Berlin lakes (as mentioned in Section 3 not all lakes are monitored), there are no prediction models in place that can offer reliable insights into future trends. Time series analysis can be used to forecast future water quality and water availability trends or generate a forecast for the present moment where live data is not available. Such forecasts can help with planning rehabilitation activities and more efficient allocation of limited resources.

As part of Pilot 3, historic water quality, water availability, weather and any other relevant data (e.g., IoT or citizen data) will be used to build and evaluate Machine Learning pipelines for predicting water quality and water availability trends. The following infrastructure will be used to facilitate building/evaluating Machine Learning pipelines: MinIO high-performance, distributed object storage system for storing data locally; KubeFlow for managing and orchestrating complex machine learning workflows; and MLFlow to facilitate the management of the machine learning lifecycle, including experimentation, reproducibility, and deployment of machine learning models.

Initial ML pipeline built by ATOS is a time series prediction for the water level for a given lake. The initial implementation is a simple model that uses only water level data, so there is a single input and a single output. The model uses a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network which is a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) suited for working with time series. The model prediction is for a single future value and it uses a sliding window to compute the next value. Figure 29 shows the output of recursive forecasting where computed values are added to the sliding window to predict future values.

Current implementation of the water availability ML pipeline is designed to start working on the pipeline and the platform itself (to test the integration of different components). The intention is to continue improving not only the results of the predictions but also the complexity of the ML model. Further discussions will be carried out with the Pilot 1 partners to identify outputs useful for the pilot stakeholders. Future work will potentially include a forecast based on historic weather data (easily accessible) and a single water level measurement.

Figure 29: Output of initial recursive forecasting for water level time series data.

6.9 COMPONENT 9 – DATA CATALOGUE AND METADATA

Within the AD4GD project, one central challenge is to ensure data that any data we use or produce in the pilot studies is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable according to the FAIR Principles⁵⁹. To facilitate this we need an accessible metadata catalogue based on an open standard. Given the AD4GD project's focus on semantic enrichment and the constraints of most existing metadata schemas, there is then an additional challenge of linking the data catalogued by AD4GD with standard vocabularies.

To address the first challenge, we have agreed to adopt GeoNetwork⁶⁰ as the primary catalogue for the AD4GD project. GeoNetwork is an open-source cataloguing tool designed for managing spatially referenced resources. It offers metadata editing, search, and interactive map visualisation capabilities, in addition to a range of federation features such as scheduled harvesting and synchronisation⁶¹. GeoNetwork can host and generate metadata records compliant with the International Standard ISO-19115- a reference model for describing information or resources with geographic extents, including their quality, spatial and temporal aspects. GeoNetwork generates a globally unique metadata identifier for each metadata record, thus allowing for referencing and linking any specific record within the catalogue as well as with other systems.

There are a number of other geospatial metadata cataloguing solutions available, such as CKAN (Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network)⁶² or GeoNode⁶³. However, in the context of European Serial Digital Interfaces (SDIs) and public geoportals, many public organisations, map agencies, and national governments in Europe use GeoNetwork to create, maintain and share their geospatial data catalogues. Consequently, GeoNetwork is designed to be compliant with the INSPIRE (Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe) Directive. It follows the INSPIRE specifications and encoding rules and links the catalogues to the INSPIRE themes and annexes. GeoNetwork utilization does not require the development of new code or approaches. However, it allows for customization of the User Interface and adding new functionalities – e.g. integration with external thesaurus/vocabularies and systems. GeoNetwork has a

⁵⁹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

⁶⁰ <https://geonetwork-opensource.org/>

⁶¹ https://geonetwork-opensource.org/_static/GeoNetwork_opensource_20_Flyer.pdf

⁶² <https://ckan.org/>

⁶³ <https://geonode.org/>

validation functionality to ensure the information is documented in compliance with all native ISO 191-family of standards and Dublin Core.

The AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue can be accessed at: <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/>.

Partners working on the AD4GD project pilots will create a metadata record per each of the datasets they will create or reuse (or per group in case of dataset series, if the management will be identical), by using the ISO 19115 available metadata templates, adequate for vector or raster data. In addition, GeoNetwork allows for importing new records in preexisting XML files. To date, 17 AD4GD datasets have been documented and their metadata published.

Data documentation activity is coordinated with the AD4GD Data Management Plan (DMP) in WP8. Each dataset or group of datasets described in AD4GD DMP will be in parallel documented and published in the AD4GD GeoNetwork, or vice versa. The next steps are to explore how to connect the GeoNetwork datastreams with our prototype of the data space, and in particular how to identify best practice for semantic linkage. There are a number of elements within the ISO metadata model which permit the insertion of vocabulary terms or references to semantic resources. For example, we can use the Citation belonging to the ISO 19115 metadata element MD_ApplicationSchemaInformation to link to the publicly-hosted data models and data schemas, or to field mappings. The MD_FeatureCatalogueDescription may also serve a similar purpose, since it too has a Citation element. This proposed relationship is the basis of the ‘usage’ linkage arrows that can be seen between Geonetwork and the Meaning Catalogue in Figure 2, Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 6, Figure 11, Figure 12, Figure 32, Figure 33 and Figure 34.

6.10 COMPONENT 10 – DATA CATALOGUE AND METADATA WITH SEMANTIC UPLIFT

As explained in Section 6.3, RDF is a key data model for supporting many of the semantic interoperability developments in AD4GD. Regarding data catalogues, DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)⁶⁴ is the most widely used RDF vocabulary. There exist some profiles of DCAT, such as GeoDCAT-AP⁶⁵ (a DCAT application profile tailored to European Union specifications), or GeoDCAT, which is currently being developed under the auspices of the Open Geospatial Consortium. DCAT, or a profile thereof, is the preferred way to represent a data catalogue in a semantically interoperable manner.

As described in Section 6.9, GeoNetwork, which has been selected as the main cataloguing system for the development of the AD4GD data space, uses ISO 19115⁶⁶ (a fixed, XML-based schema) as its metadata schema. Being able to represent GeoNetwork metadata in a semantically-compatible format would bring many advantages to the project, such as the ability to integrate different data catalogues into a “virtual super-catalogue”, whether they are supported by GeoNetwork, other ISO 19115 implementations, or any other tool or service that can produce DCAT/GeoDCAT metadata. Data space consumers (both human and machine) could then query and explore this “virtual super-catalogue” in order to locate and retrieve datasets that they may be interested in, in an interoperable manner and without having to concern themselves with the specific products or systems employed by the data providers.

There is some existing work on an XSLT-based⁶⁷ transformation to convert ISO 19115 to GeoDCAT-AP. This transformation needs to be adapted to conform to DCAT/GeoDCAT, as well as to the specific ISO 19115 implementation employed in the AD4GD (GeoNetwork), including any AD4GD-specific metadata defined for GeoNetwork. Much of the existing XSLT transformation will be reused, but it is necessary to adapt it to the ISO 19115 implementation used (GeoNetwork) and to the desired output format (DCAT/GeoDCAT instead of GeoDCAT-AP). New code will be developed to query the GeoNetwork catalogue using the product’s API, and

⁶⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

⁶⁵ <https://semiceu.github.io/GeoDCAT-AP/drafts/latest/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html>

⁶⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/xslt-30/>

to extract the ISO 19115 XML descriptions that will be converted using the aforementioned XSLT transformation. Additionally, the results of the transformation (which will be in RDF in Turtle⁶⁸ format) will need to be stored in an RDF database (or “triplestore”) and published according to semantic web guidelines, for which further software development will need to be done.

A client for the GeoNetwork API will be developed that will retrieve the metadata for all datasets in ISO 19115 (XML) format. These XML documents will then be transformed into DCAT/GeoDCAT, and the results uploaded to an RDF triplestore. A proof-of-concept implementation of the GeoNetwork client + catalogue records transformation has already been developed to showcase the feasibility of the overall system, and has been shown to successfully transform the existing AD4GD catalogue hosted by CREAM (~17 datasets).

The next steps for development are:

- Improving the output RDF metadata, especially with regard to GeoDCAT compliance.
- Developing validation, enrichment and upload mechanisms for the outputs.
- Deploying an end-to-end test instance of the system.
- Testing implementations for federated, semantic catalogues.
- Carrying out performance tests and studying and applying potential optimizations.
- Crafting a set of sample or template queries representing potential use cases for data consumers.

The goal at the end of the AD4GD project is a fully functional solution that can retrieve metadata from GeoNetwork (and potentially other ISO 19115-compatible catalogues), convert it to DCAT/GeoDCAT, and publish it so that it can be queried by clients, as well as a sample interface to access or explore this metadata (such as a set of template queries).

6.11 COMPONENT 11 – DATA TRUSTWORTHINESS FRAMEWORK

Observational data from IoT sensors is highly heterogeneous and often of unknown or poorly characterised reliability. In order to better work with this data, a framework for assessing and annotating the data with estimates of its reliability and trustworthiness is needed.

There is a large body of existing research into the topic within the meteorological community as it relates to assimilating data from calibrated weather stations and the (operational) control and assessment of their quality. There are also existing standardised information models such as QualityML (<https://qualityml.org/>) and SensorML (<https://www.ogc.org/standard/sensorml/>) that relate to the question of data trustworthiness.

Work is ongoing to determine what kinds of trustworthiness information would be most appropriate for pilot 3. This could include per-sensor estimates of measurement uncertainty, a more abstract quality score or a corrected value. Which of these may be best suited to the context is yet to be determined.

The concept as it will be implemented in pilot 3 is to create a generalised statistical model that would perform data driven outlier filtering, calibration and bias correction using the air quality and weather forecast as a reference and feature input. We will use ground based reference measurements from the EEA to assess the quality of this correction model. There are several hundred reference stations across Europe and 13,000 Sensor.Community stations.

The next steps involve further optimisation of the statistical model. ECMWF will start running the model in near real time which will make the output available along with the original data. We will integrate this with the semantic vocabulary terms defined in WP1 to ensure consistent conceptual representation of measured phenomena and quality descriptors. This work will be carried out primarily within Task 4.4, and will be documented in Deliverable 4.2.

⁶⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

The goal at the end of the AD4GD project is a prototype system for the end-to-end ingestion and quality annotation of IoT observational data into ECMWF infrastructure. This data will be accessible via a semantically enriched API, and we will make the quality assessments and usability guidance available in an open and standardised manner so that producers and users of IoT and CitSci air quality data can benefit from and possibly replicate the quality assurance procedure followed.

6.12 COMPONENT 12 – GDDS SEMANTIC TERMS - RAINBOW SERVER

The pilot studies identified for the AD4GD project have allowed us to explore and identify a range of semantic resources which can potentially be used to link across domains, spatial scales and data types, allowing a more rigorous and principled combination of data and services to support Green Deal decision-making. These vocabularies cover phenomena such as measurable variables and their units, sensor types, experimental and survey protocols, quality criteria and many more. Semantic enrichment with such terms (e.g. Section 6.3) allows easier assessment of data fitness-for-purpose since the thresholds and priorities of a particular analysis can be mapped to the characteristics of the data.

Harmonisation of different vocabulary terms which refer to the same concept, and maintenance of the relationships between terms (e.g. "broader", "narrower", "equal to") allow mapping between datasets and services to discover datasets which record the same phenomenon in the same way, and so support aggregation and meta-analysis. Ideally, ontologies and vocabularies should be maintained by international bodies that have capabilities to manage such resources and offer stable unique persistent identifiers to support FAIR discovery and use. However, linkage and interaction between these hosted resources will always be necessary within the GDDS because of the wide range of domains and disciplines involved in complex environmental challenges, and the range of different authorities and institutions involved. Therefore, to host AD4GD's GDIM, we require an easily accessible and extensible semantic resource which is capable of supporting formal semantic linkage out to other repositories and stores, such as LifeWatch EcoPortal and other Ontoportals, the NERC (Natural Environment Research Council) vocabulary server and the EIONet (European Environment Information and Observation Network) data dictionary. The OGC Registry for Accessible Identifiers of Names and Basic Ontologies for the Web (RAINBOW) server (formerly OGC Definitions Server) already exists and is capable of supporting the profiling of complex models. It will be used within the AD4GD project (and beyond) to host all relevant ontologies and the GDIM.

The OGC RAINBOW server offers stable web addresses (URIs) to unambiguously identify concepts. It supports creation of vocabularies with uniquely defined terms. The server also offers a Continuous Integration/Continuous Testing/Continuous Deployment (CI/CT/CD) implementation of best practices which ensures that corrections and refinements to the components of an information model do not introduce unforeseen inconsistencies (for more details see D1.3, Section 3.1 Overview). Development work will focus on transforming controlled vocabularies into RDF format and aligning terms in different vocabularies to avoid duplication of terms (e.g., identifying "broader", "narrower", "equal to" relationships). More technical detail may be found in D1.2 and D1.3 of this project, and an example of one of the AD4GD-specific resources is shown in Figure 30.

The AD4GD development RAINBOW environment can be accessed at: <http://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/>.

In the context of AD4GD, elements representing parts of the following Essential Variables / Essential Variable Products and controlled vocabularies have so far been transformed to RDF and added to the RAINBOW server:

Essential Agriculture Variables - codelist scheme:

<http://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/object?uri=http%3A//w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/eav>

Essential Biodiversity Variables:

<http://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/object?uri=http%3A//w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ebv>

Essential Climate Variables:

<http://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/object?uri=https%3A//w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ecv>

Sensors:

<https://defs-dev.opengis.net/vocprez-hosted/object?uri=https%3A//w3id.org/ad4gd/sensors>

These complement (and can be used alongside) a wide range of GDDS-relevant terms already hosted on the production RAINBOW server (see <https://defs.opengis.net/vocprez/vocab>).

Figure 30: An example sensor entry from the RAINBOW server which supports the air quality pilot. It represents a temperature and humidity sensor commonly used in low-cost air quality measuring stations including the Sensor.Community AirRohr.. This entry may be accessed and explored at: <https://w3id.org/ad4gd/sensors/various/DHT22>.

The next steps will focus on:

- continuing to add and refine Essential Variables and Essential Variable Products as controlled vocabularies;
- transforming and adding new vocabularies and terms and relations between them, including:
 - EIONET;
 - M3-lite ontology;
 - sensor and sensor platform descriptions for all three pilots;
 - quality terms.
- making tools easily accessible and usable by data and service providers;

in order to make an integrated and extensible GDIM accessible via the OGC RAINBOW.

7 ASSESSMENT OF INTERIM PILOT STATUS / PRIORITISATION OF MILESTONES FOR MONTHS 19-30

7.1 PILOT 1: WATER POLLUTION

Several sources of data for the pilot are already accessible by open and standardised APIs, including the SENTINEL data which has been used to experimentally evaluate chlorophyll concentrations (see Figure 31), and a range of environmental, cadastral and administrative boundaries, which are made available through the Senate's 'FIS-Broker' platform. This latter data includes lake boundaries, watersheds and some groundwater mapping, and also some socioeconomic data which may be useful in future analysis of ecosystem service demand. CitSci data pipelines, including an adapted version of the CrowdWater app are also to be developed within the coming year (see below).

Figure 31: A Google Earth Engine prototyping exercise (extending the approach of Cardall et al. 2021) was carried out by AU and KWB to evaluate the feasibility of chlorophyll monitoring for the smaller lakes with SENTINEL data. A good estimation of trend appears possible, using a set of conversion parameters derived from Ogashawara et al (2021). For any extension of this work, ground truth data from *in situ* sensors will be required (a) to compute locally-appropriate parameters and (b) to verify the accuracy of chl-a predictions. The above screenshot shows mean chlorophyll-a for Ploetzensee over one year, with the time series for a selected pixel shown below.

In situ sensor data is not yet available for the specific small lakes to be studied, and this is particularly important for benchmarking EO data and for calibrating its analysis, since 'ground truth' from smaller lakes in Berlin is so sparse in space and time. Three small lakes have been identified at which the pilot approaches will be developed and calibrated. To start with, oxygen sensors are to be installed in three selected small lakes around month 20 by KWB, in close collaboration with the Berlin stakeholders, including the Berlin district authorities who are responsible for lake monitoring. *In situ* measurements of temperature, nutrients and pH will also be derived from small lakes during 2024 in partnership with local schools, using low-cost devices. To monitor lake water levels, KWB are engaging with the developers of the CrowdWater app in

order to produce a version of the monitoring app appropriate for lakes, and this is expected to be deployed with a set of volunteers in 2025.

In the meantime, it is possible to access analogous sensor data from other lakes via the Senate's 'Wasserportal', and this has been experimentally ingested and semantically uplifted (see Sections 6.3, 6.4 and 6.5) using terms from the meaning service (Section 6.12) to generate several live STA data streams (Section 6.5)⁶⁹. Thus, for many of the anticipated new sources of data, it is possible to prepare the pipeline in advance since their formats and semantic aspects are well-characterised. This means that, as it comes onstream, new data can be semantically enriched following the methods developed in WP 1 and 3, and ingested by ATOS to build and validate prediction models for water availability and quality. The algorithm and protocol for the water quality index and water availability index (WQI and WAI) is still under development (see Section 3) but a data and analysis pipeline has been prepared by ATOS, involving ingestion of weather and sensor data to a Minio data store which feeds models implemented with KubeFlow and deployed using MLFlow. An experimental prediction model for water level has been developed (see Section 6.8) which acts as a proxy for water availability. This model is ready to be extended to covariates (primarily precipitation) which will allow more refined forecasting.

Metadata formats for the data outputs are still to be decided: the metadata should incorporate some provenance information including model parameters and processing steps, and include terms from the RAINBOW server as keywords and conceptual descriptions wherever possible. In order to incorporate descriptions of models and model runs, we propose to exploit artifacts from MLFlow execution tracking⁷⁰. An ISO->GeoDCAT transformation service is already available which will ease the provision of metadata in GeoDCAT format if requested by the user. Limited metadata is available for the STA data streams⁷¹, and this will be extended in the coming months.

The 'Splashboard' UI client and the service interface will be defined and developed via 2 iterations of working prototypes, to be tested by end users between months 18 and 30. Priorities for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months of the project are summarised in Table 2, and allocated to the responsible project partners.

⁶⁹ e.g. [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Datastreams\(18\)/Thing](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Datastreams(18)/Thing)

⁷⁰ <https://mlflow.org/docs/latest/tracking.html>

⁷¹ e.g. [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams\(23\)/Sensor](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Sensor)

Pilot 1: Water Quality

AD4GD

Figure 32: Water pilot priorities for the next 12 months. Multiple coloured boxes indicate that there are planned milestones at more than one of the 3-month timesteps (see table below for details). Metadata will continue to be produced and published continuously for project data inputs / outputs throughout months 19-30.

Table 2: Priorities for the water pilot for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months.

Component / Activity	Lead (support)	Actions	Concrete outcome(s)	Month
3 - semantic uplift	PSNC, OGC (KWB, CREAM)	Field mapping and semantic modelling of anticipated CitSci water observations (e.g. temperature and pH measured by schools)	Published field mapping available and ready for use	21
12 - RAINBOW	OGC (PSNC, KWB, CREAM)	Publication of semantic resources required to support understanding and linkage of school-volunteered data	Published resources (e.g. terms to represent measurement protocols, observed properties and CitSci activities)	21
4 - TAPIS / 3 - FROST	CREAF, IoT Lab	Use of semantic mappings and format transformation to publish standardised data on small lakes volunteered by schools.	Working data services, updated with new submissions	24
3 - semantic uplift	PSNC, OGC (KWB, CREAM)	Field mapping and semantic modelling of Crowdwater observations	Published field mapping available and ready for use	21
12 - RAINBOW	OGC (PSNC, KWB, CREAM)	Publication of semantic resources required to support understanding and linkage of Crowdwater data	Published resources (e.g. terms to represent measurement protocols, observed properties and CitSci activities)	21
4 - TAPIS / 3 - FROST	CREAF, IoT Lab	Re-use of Crowdwater semantic mapping to generate FROST server streams from Crowdwater data	Working data services, working in near-real time	30

Component / Activity	Lead (support)	Actions	Concrete outcome(s)	Month
3 - semantic uplift	PSNC (KWB)	Field mapping and semantic modelling of new <i>in situ</i> IoT sensors / observations	Published field mapping available and ready for use	21
12 - RAINBOW	OGC (PSNC, KWB)	Publication of semantic resources required to support understanding and linkage of new IoT sensor data	Published resources (e.g. terms to represent measurement protocols, observed properties and sensor characteristics)	21
5 - IoT-> STA	IoT Lab	Publication of datastreams from AD4GD-installed IoT sensors on FROST server	Working data streams for oxygen	24
9 - metadata	IoT Lab	Full metadata for FROST server AD4GD data streams - format to be decided.	Full discoverable metadata for water data streams	24
WQI/WAI definition EO	KWB (AU, ATOS)	Validation and verification of WQI/WAI methodology based on remote sensing	WQI/ WAI EO methodology for use by ATOS and KWB	24
WQI/ WAI definition (<i>in situ</i>)	KWB (ATOS)	Decision on observables and parameters for <i>in situ</i> WQI and WAI index	WQI/ WAI <i>in situ</i> methodology for use by ATOS	21
8 - water quality / availability prediction	ATOS (IoT Lab, KWB)	Ingestion of KWB <i>in situ</i> sensor data to analysis platform	Demonstrable pipeline for water IoT data ingestion, statistics on performance and data volume	24
8 - water quality / availability prediction	ATOS (CREAF, KWB)	Ingestion of CrowdWater data to analysis platform	Demonstrable pipeline for water CitSci data ingestion, statistics on performance and data volume	27
8 - water availability prediction	ATOS (KWB)	Refinement of water level model using precipitation data and groundwater	Defined model with performance statistics	21
8 - water quality prediction	ATOS (KWB)	Development of water quality model(s) using <i>in situ</i> and possibly EO data	Defined model with performance statistics	24
8 - water quality / availability prediction	ATOS, FIT (KWB)	Agreement of output format for data and metadata, and API standard to be used for data exchange.	Defined API signature for client access	21
GDSS interfaces / clients	FIT (KWB)	First working prototype of Splashboard client for stakeholder testing.	Working prototype of Splashboard client which accepts user input and constructs a request to ATOS service	21
GDSS interfaces / clients	FIT (ATOS)	Connection by Splashboard prototype interface to at least one form of output data from ATOS platform (probably water level predictions)	Real-time retrieval and visualisation of water predictions in the Splashboard	24
GDSS interfaces / clients	FIT (ATOS, KWB)	Second working prototype of Splashboard client for stakeholder testing.	Working Splashboard client incorporating changes from stakeholder feedback	27
GDSS interfaces / clients	FIT (ATOS, KWB)	Final version of Splashboard client for evaluation of performance, scaling and usability.	Final client with end-to-end interaction between user and analysis platform	30

7.2 PILOT 2: BIODIVERSITY

The following input datasets have been ingested and processed to obtain FLC outputs:

- LULC raster data
- Impedance data derived from LULC data and based on expert knowledge
- OSM vector data and GBIF occurrences data obtained through open and accessible APIs

The following output datasets have been generated:

- ICT raster data from MiraMon
- Data on connectivity indices and habitat corridors from Graphab
- Refined and enriched LULC data

The preprocessing module which enriches LULC maps with linear features from OSM has been completed and the first draft is available on Github⁷². Further improvement of code in terms of performance and flexibility and retrieving other categories of OSM datasets are still required to develop a generic approach to the FLC computation.

Optimisation of Graphab and MiraMon applications through dockerised applications on the HPC cluster, multi-platform deployment and enhancing their performance are the important tasks to be completed in the future. To provide an automatic linking and cross-walking of outputs and Bioconnect GUI, the workflow to produce templated metadata that is automatically enriched with relevant terms representing Essential Biodiversity Variables Products should be developed.

First instances of Open Data Cube and HPC have been created to bypass hardware capabilities which is considered to be one of the cornerstones in Pilot 2 due to the complex mathematical basis of both Graphab and Miramon. However, the working instances of HPC computations and Open Data Cube need to be further tested through increasing the complexity of queries, building a WMS/WCS browser on top of Open Data Cube, and testing / implementing MPI mode on the HPC cluster. Since the first HPC test has been successful in increasing Graphab performance, a dockerised stand-alone Miramon application (currently in development) should also be able to execute computations at a new state-of-the-art level when deployed on the HPC. This will allow faster and more efficient computation of FLC in MiraMon for higher spatial resolution (with smaller pixels). This will also allow for testing the application in Wine or Docker and trying to run it in other environments.

FLC computations may be performed in other ways, potentially consuming less hardware capabilities and taking less time - through ML processing. Therefore, this experimental step is also planned to be tested on the ATOS cluster to predict future FLC scenarios, train the model and verify it by LULC and FLC data at previous timestamps.

At the same time, to increase the plausibility of outputs and ensure the practical and scientific implementation of connectivity computation workflows, it is necessary to build a dialog with relevant stakeholders, detect concrete species, sites of interest, any new sources of relevant data, and update user stories from various stakeholders, including consulting ones, governmental and CitSci projects. Moreover, execution of connectivity computations on specific areas will significantly reduce processing time.

In situ sensor data from camera traps have yet to be obtained and analysed. Camera trap data may be useful to verify presence and migration routes on concrete sites by key species of interest, but still requires edge processing to optimise access and increase performance of data access. Edge processing of camera trap data from the Cos4Cloud project and publication of data streams on FROST server are suggested as experimental steps in Pilot 2.

Alternatively, another source of species presence/absence is yet to be analysed, in the form of the B3 occurrence cubes for priority species for Catalonia region. These will be produced by GBIF from their full set

⁷² <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2/tree/main/preprocessing>

of observations (i.e. the same data repository which is currently being queried directly via existing APIs, The experimental data cube format is designed to ease specific spatio-temporal and thematic queries, and will be evaluated for its potential to enrich FLC computation modules and verify connectivity outputs. Suitability data from B3 cube may be considered as a further experimental step for the further improvement of FLC computations through updating one of the input datasets – habitat impedance. Even though the implementation of connectors is currently facing numerous issues (see Section 7.2) the potential connection to access data from B3 cube should be tested.

Figure 33: Biodiversity Pilot priorities for the next 12 months. Multiple coloured boxes indicate that there are planned milestones at more than one of the 3-month timesteps (see table below for details). Metadata will continue to be produced and published continuously for project data inputs / outputs throughout months 19-30.

Meanwhile, GBIF datasets (CSV and Darwin Core package) have been retrieved and analysed with a focus on the provenance of data, including CitSci sources. GBIF data can be incorporated into Pilot 2 to verify the presence of species in critical sites in three different ways: through STAplus service (already developed), in occurrence data within data cubes, or provide the additional means of visualisation for Bioconnect GUI through OGC API.

To support the visual representation of data used and computed through different stages in Pilot 2, the Bioconnect GUI client and its service interface will be further defined and developed via iterations of working prototypes, to be tested by end users (months 24-30).

The final integrated system developed in Pilot 2 should be able to execute series of FLC computations swiftly through the dockerised applications of MiraMon and Graphab on the HPC cluster, preprocessing and

ingesting input data from the Open Data Cube instance, enriched with automatically produced metadata through the meaning catalogue and mapped EBVs, and be accessed and visualised through Bioconnect GUI. On top of that, users may be able to compare results obtained to species occurrences data derived from GBIF API, B3 cube, other camera traps and accessed through OGC APIs and STApplus service.

Priorities for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months of the project are summarised in Table 3, and allocated to the responsible project partners.

Table 3: Priorities for the biodiversity pilot for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months.

Component Activity /	Lead (support) partners	Actions	Concrete outcome(s)	Month
Stakeholder engagement	FIT, CREAM (AU)	Engagement with relevant stakeholders including at least 1 environmental consultancy and at least 1 CitSci initiative	1) Two or more new user stories documented. 2) Listing of any new sources of relevant data. 3) Report on regional priorities in terms of particularly sensitive species and areas with fragile connectivity.	21
7 - Preprocessing connectivity data	AU	Finalise, optimise and increase performance of existing code, including tests of applicability of auxiliary data from Catalonian government.	1) open refined codebase published 2) examples of enriched and refined LULC data published, with metadata	21
6 - data cubes	CREAF	Creating a Jupyter Notebook to access OpenDataCube	Published Jupyter Notebook to access input and output data on OpenDataCube	21
6 - data cubes	CREAF	OpenDataCube ingestion with new sources of auxiliary data (bioindicators, bioclimatic, socioeconomic when relevant, etc). and outputs, and OGC API-standardised browser on top of the Data Cube	Accessible input and output data deployed in Open Data Cube with OGC-standard browser* on top of the Data Cube to present visual outputs of the queries and multidimensional analysis. (*WMS/WCS or OGC API maps and OGC API coverages)	21
6 - data cubes	CREAF	To encode GBIF occurrence data in FROST server to show interoperability among different systems, in particular, connect them as single observations (not per pixel) into the OGC API standardised browser running on top of the DataCube.	Accessible GBIF with WMS/WCS browser	24
6 - data cubes	AU (CREAF)	Publish Graphab outputs in Open Data Cube or Rasdaman	Accessible output data deployed in ODC/Rasdaman, stats on output data from Miramon and Graphab.	21
6 - data cubes	AU (CREAF)	Consume occurrence cubes from B3 project for at least one priority species for the region, and perform the integration between B3 Species occurrence cube and Open Data Cube.	Occurrence data successfully ingested and aligned with AD4GD results for verification / visualisation	21
6 - data cubes	AU (CREAF)	Consume suitability cubes from B3 cube for at least one priority species for the region, and re-use FLC computation modules (experimental step)	Success in computing maps of 'suitable habitat connectivity', updating input data on habitat impedance (for connectivity workflow)	24
7 - Implementation MiraMon software	CREAF, AU	Deploy MiraMon connectivity application as a re-usable and stand-alone component and test it on Wine/Docker.	Producing easily accessible MiraMon outputs through self-contained dockers (presumably, through Wine)	21

Component Activity /	Lead (support) partners	Actions	Concrete outcome(s)	Month
7 - HPC	PSNC (AU)	Complete and report Graphab performance testing of scenarios (including native MPI mode and postprocessing code - compressing, filtering outputs) on the HPC cluster.	Performance stats of computation, deployed Graphab outputs	21
7 - HPC	PSNC (CREAF)	Perform testing of dockerized Miramon connectivity application on the HPC cluster	Performance stats of computation, deployed Miramon outputs	24
9 - Metadata automation	CREAF, AU	Automate metadata production from ISO 19115 templates in GeoNetwork	Templated ISO metadata published in Geonetwork.	21
9 - Metadata automation	CREAF, AU, OGC	Link metadata to the data including semantics (OGC Rainbow Definition Server (Essential Variables).	1) Producing meaning/mapping catalogue with templated ISO metadata enriched with agreed vocabulary terms and links to csv-w files. 2) Meaning catalogue in place.	24
12 - GDDS clients and Interfaces	FIT (CREAF, AU)	Build a connection between connectivity computation workflow and Bioconnect GUI tool	First working prototype of Bioconnect GUI tool for end-user evaluation, connecting to the computation workflow	24
8 - ML implementation	ATOS, CREAF	Experimental study on applicability of ML to predict connectivity. Two approaches to test - Deep Learning and generative AI (learning patterns of land-use/land-cover and connectivity data). Verify outputs for 2022 by data of previous timestamps (1987-2017).	Report on feasibility of ML to compute connectivity, prediction model (tentatively)	27
12 - GDDS clients and Interfaces	FIT, CREAF, AU	Integration of GBIF WMS in the BioConnect front end GUI for visualisation.	Second working prototype with enriched means of visualisation (species occurrences)	27
5 - IoT	CREAF	Deciding on hardware and deploying camera traps on points of interest revealed through interviews with stakeholders	Real image data from camera traps	24
5 - IoT	IoT LAB (CREAF)	Edge processing of camera trap data (for instance, images from the Cos4Cloud project), publication of datastreams on FROST server (experimental)	Working datastreams for camera trap data (filtered, reorganised and optimised sensor data) with full metadata	27
12 - GDDS clients and Interfaces	FIT, CREAF, AU	Integration of <i>in situ</i> sensors data in the BioConnect front end GUI for visualisation.	Second working prototype with enriched means of visualisation (species occurrences)	27
12 - GDDS clients and Interfaces	CREAF, AU	Final update of all workflows in open-access way (Github, JupyterLab)	Working codes in repositories to access data and execute connectivity computations	30
12 - GDDS clients and Interfaces	FIT (CREAF, AU)	Finalise Bioconnect GUI Tool	Final working prototype of Bioconnect GUI tool	30
2 - connectors	PSNC / ATOS (CREAF, AU, ECMWF)	Test connectors for contractual access to data from sister project B3	Protocol for connector use, or specific list of barriers preventing use.	24

7.3 PILOT 3: AIR QUALITY

This pilot study was initially formulated with a hypothetical focus on evaluating the possible added value of socio-economic data (e.g. traffic counts, energy production and transfer) and of IoT (low-cost sensors) to estimate greenhouse gas concentrations and emissions on a local to city scale. The pilot focus has now shifted in scope to the highly topical subject of air pollution, and in particular to evaluating the scientific value of IoT based observations such as those collected by CitSci volunteers in Sensor.Community and other initiatives. Within Pilot 3, ECMWF will make a preliminary study of the reliability and trustworthiness of a range of IoT and CitSci observations, with a view that in the future it may be beneficial to incorporate information from these IoT sources into the forecast model to increase its granularity.

The pilot was scheduled to begin in month 13, but a range of preparatory activities have informed its development so far. During the first year of the project, ECMWF explored the possible use of sensor add-ons in DHL trucks in Northern Italy. Leading on from this, ECMWF investigated ways to build on current work at AU with Air Quality (AQ) sensors (aggregating data from Plume Flows, Earthsense Zephyrs and Sensor.Community kits). These approaches / code will be re-used and combined with ECMWF's in-house data pipelines as appropriate to support ingestion of AQ data from citizen initiatives and IoT networks which currently publish their data via non-standard APIs. The Aston Air Quality Dashboard ⁷³ (see Section 6.1) has been used to ingest data from multiple sensors (including mobile devices) and these data exemplars were used at the project hackathons in Birmingham (October 23) and Torino (February 24) to kick start experiments on integration and semantic enrichment. Examples of raw data extracted from various sensors show how necessary the semantic mapping is: the "Observed Properties" values and the "Units of Measure" are provided in many different ways and opportunities for semantic uplift exist.

In the next months, the practical usability of CitSci / IoT air quality observations will be investigated for different regions in Europe (e.g. Benelux, Northern Italy) that represent different air quality regimes. To this end, investigations will consider the unique regional characteristics such as orography, air pollution sources, or the impact of different weather patterns.

This work will also connect to the semantic interoperability framework defined in WP1, in particular we are starting to define vocabularies relevant to the project and link those terms to existing terms with the RDF model defined by PSNC and OGC (see also Sections 6.3 and 6.12). This will enable the publication of near-real-time data streams as STA / STApplus services for use both within the project and beyond in the wider GDDS. Validating and annotating the IoT data will also serve as a starting point for the development of the data trustworthiness framework in T4.4.

Priorities for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months of the project are summarised in Table 4, and allocated to the responsible project partners. They are illustrated in Figure 34.

⁷³ <https://aston-air-quality.web.app/sensor-platforms>

Pilot 3: Air Quality

AD4GD

Figure 34: Air pollution pilot priorities for the next 12 months. Multiple coloured boxes indicate that there are planned milestones at more than one of the 3-month timesteps (see table below for details). Metadata will continue to be produced and published continuously for project data inputs / outputs throughout months 19-30.

Table 4: Priorities for the air quality pilot for the next 3, 6, 9 and 12 months.

Component / Activity	Lead (support) partners	Actions	Concrete outcome(s)	Month
1 - AQ Ingestion	AU, ECMWF	Review and refactor open codebase, identify modules for re-use and combination with OpenAQ services and with ECMWF in-house approach.	Finalised documented pipeline and code for IoT / CS AQ data ingestion	21
1 - AQ Ingestion	AU, ECMWF	Create a repository of test IoT AQ data for use in later steps.	Project repository with examples of each AQ IoT /community sensor data type	21
1 - AQ Ingestion	AU, ECMWF	Create and document live API access to ingested IoT data.	Documentation of the APIs available to access the data ingested into AU and ECMWFs IoT infrastructure.	21
12 - RAINBOW	OGC (CREAF, PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Enable synchronisation / update of semantic definitions by partners (and future GDSS users)	Github action to push updates to RAINBOW	21
12 - RAINBOW	OGC (CREAF, PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Add or correct all relevant air quality vocabularies and air quality sensor/platform descriptions to RAINBOW server. Connect "same as" air quality terms and create relationships between sensors, platforms and observed properties.	Final version of air quality vocabularies (and relationships between terms) and air quality sensor descriptions are on RAINBOW (verified and correct).	21
3 - Semantic uplift	PSNC (OGC, ECMWF, AU)	Create or correct mappings of data field names to vocabulary terms for air quality data from Sensor.Community, Zephyr, Plume, PurpleAir.	Final air quality mapping files are verified and correct, and available in an easily-readable format (e.g. YAML).	21

Component / Activity	Lead (support) partners	Actions	Concrete outcome(s)	Month
3 - Semantic uplift	PSNC (OGC, ECMWF, AU)	Convert CSV air quality data samples from community sensors (Sensor.Community, Zephyr, Plume, PurpleAir) to STA format using RDF approach (comparative method A).	Samples of air quality data from each provider is available on https://www.foodie-cloud.org/... (verified and correct).	21
5 - Semantic uplift	IoT Lab (OGC, ECMWF, AU)	Convert CSV air quality data samples from Sensor.Community, Zephyr, Plume, PurpleAir to FROST server data streams (comparative method B).	Samples of air quality data from each provider is available on https://frost.iotlab.com/.. (verified and correct).	21
9 - metadata	PSNC (CREAF, OGC, ECMWF, AU)	Full metadata for RDF data samples created using GeoNetwork.	Full discoverable metadata for air quality data samples that were transformed to STA using RDF implementation.	21
9 - metadata	ECMWF (CREAF, OGC, PSNC, AU)	Full metadata for IoT data accessible from ECMWF using GeoNetwork.	Full discoverable metadata for air quality data that is stored in the ECMWF ecosystem.	21
4 - TAPIS	CREAF	Connect TAPIS to PSNC STA implementation to ingest and retrieve static examples of air quality data (test feasibility).	TAPIS successfully used to upload and download example air quality data from PSNC RDF implementation of STA services.	24
3 - Semantic uplift	OGC (PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Create interface (e.g. Jupyter Notebook(s)) that will act as a GUI and allow mapping of data fields to vocabulary terms in RAINBOW to create SPARQL mappings file.	User-friendly interface that supports mapping of field names to vocabulary terms in RAINBOW to create SPARQL mapping files.	21
3 - Semantic uplift	OGC (PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Create interface to allow conversion of air quality data CSV files to STA format using RDF approach (make data available via https://www.foodie-cloud.org/).	User-friendly interface and proven dataset transformation.	21
3 - Semantic uplift	OGC (PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Create interface to allow querying of air quality data in STA format (using RDF approach) from https://www.foodie-cloud.org/ without having to construct STA or SPARQL queries (user friendly interface).	User-friendly interface and proven dataset transformation.	21
3 - Semantic uplift	OGC (PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Agree on and prioritise the User Stories that will be implemented for Air Quality semantic uplift (user stories defined by LB (AU) and TH (ECMWF)).	Agreed on and prioritised list of User Stories to be implemented.	21
3 - Semantic uplift	OGC (PSNC, ECMWF, AU)	Evaluate success in implementing User Stories described above.	Internal reports at 3-month intervals on testing and performance.	24,27,30
3 - Semantic uplift	PSNC (OGC, ECMWF, AU)	Live air quality data ingestion and transformation pipeline using RDF to STA approach. Use the OpenAQ API (or liaise with ECMWF to re-use their ingestion pipeline to retrieve data) for semantic enrichment.	Live data streams from the OpenAQ API or ECMWF are semantically uplifted and transformed to STA format using RDF approach.	24
4 - TAPIS	CREAF	Connect TAPIS to PSNC STA implementation of live data stream to ingest and retrieve air quality data (test feasibility).	TAPIS successfully used to download live air quality data from PSNC RDF implementation of STA services.	27
? - Data Trustworthiness Framework	ECMWF	Build a simple correction model for IoT air quality observations. Deploy this model such that a user can request corrected version of sensor.community data in real or near real time.		27

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9 APPENDIX A1

Pilot 1 Lake Splashboard Tool

User Journey

Figure 35 shows the Pilot 1 User Journey from the perspective of a Berlin District Lake Manager, identified in the Pilot Kick-Off Workshop.

Figure 35: Pilot 1 User Journey from the perspective of a Berlin District Lake Manager, who decides on measures for small lakes.

Value Proposition Statement

For Berlin District Lake Manager who wants to improve the management of small urban lakes, Lake Splashboard is a tool that displays indicators of water quality of small urban lakes and their evolution (historical data/trend).

Co-Designing Interfaces based on the User Journey

Based on the Pilot 1 User Journey, an initial prototype of the Lake Splashboard tool was created.. This tool is intended to help the decision makers to manage the small lakes by displaying relevant data. The tool will be developed iteratively with the involvement of stakeholders and the user group. The main functionalities are as follows:

- Ranking of all small lakes in Berlin based on the developed Lake Index (to be defined in this project);
- Detailed information for each small urban lake;
- Possibility to upload data.

Figure 36: Pilot 1 Lake Splashboard GUI Prototype.

Pilot 2 BioConnect Tool

User Journey

Figure 37 shows the Pilot 2 User Journey from the perspective of a researcher at CREAM who has the goal of generating the multidimensional connectivity maps, identified in the Pilot Kick-Off Workshop.

Figure 37: User Journey from the perspective of a Researcher at CREAM.

10 APPENDIX A2

<i>Initial LULC categories of MUCSC maps</i>	<i>CODE</i>	<i>Aggregated LULC categories of MUCSC maps</i>
Continental waters	1	Aquatic environments
Wetland vegetation		
Infrastructures	2	Urban and industrial areas and infrastructures
Sparse edifications, urbanizations		
Urban areas		
Industrial and commercial areas		
Dryland herbaceous crops	3	Herbaceous crops
Irrigated herbaceous crops		
Rice fields		
Dryland fruit trees	4	Woody crops
Irrigated fruit trees		
Vineyards		
Citrus fruits trees		
Highland meadows	5	Meadows and shrublands
Shrublands		
Midland meadows		
Burnt areas		
Lowland meadows		
Sclerophyll forests	6	Forests
Deciduous forests		
Coniferous forests		
Areas with little or no vegetation	7	Denuded areas
Snow drifts		
Sand dunes and beaches		
Marine waters		NODATA

11 APPENDIX A3

Comparison of Graphab and Conefor features

Parameters	Graphab v. 2.8	Conefor v. 2.6
Licence	GNU GPL	GNU GPL
Graphical user interface	+	+
Command line interface	+	+
Programming language	Java	C++
Operating systems	Linux, Windows, Mac	Linux, Windows, Mac
<i>Input data (mandatory)</i>		
LULC	Image raster file (tif, ascii, rst) categorised by types	-
Minimum patch area	User given decimal value (ha)	-
Maximum distance to consider edges	User given decimal value (m)	-
Nodes	-	Txt file
Connections	-	Txt file
Distance and probabilities	-	Maximum distance to migrate and probability to be found at this distance (user given integer or decimal values)
<i>Input data (optional)</i>		
Cost of connectivity along the edges	User given decimal values or image raster file - tif, ascii	-
Absence-presence points of species	shp or csv files with longitude and latitude columns, binary columns on presence and absence of species + 2 input values - distance to migrate and probability to be found at this distance	-
Digital elevation model	Image raster file (tif, ascii)	-
Changes in LULC	Polygons with an attribute of LULC type, according to raster file (shp)	-
Maximum landscape attribute	-	User given numerical value (area of patch covering all habitats)
<i>Output data</i>		
Connectivity indices	CSV table with decimal values of indices chosen by user from 3 families for each centroid (node) of habitat patches (weighted, area, topological) - 21 indices in total	ASCII text file with decimal values of indices for each node or overall (global) index values

Components of graph	Graph components may be exported (gpkg, shp, txt) through GUI	ASCII text file listing the number of component graph for each node
Patches	All spatial polygonal features with habitats, according to user chosen LULC types (shp and tif)	-
Links	Line features with all links created during the graph computation (shp)	ASCII text file with binary value for each node referring to the existence of a link (true or false)
Voronoi polygons	Interim polygons created during the graph computation (shp)	-
Probabilities of dispersal	-	ASCII text file listing dispersal probabilities between each pair of nodes
<i>Built-in modules</i>		
Species distribution models	+	-
Modelling of ecological corridors	+	-
GIS modules	QGIS	QGIS, ArcGIS, Guidos
Other packages	graph4lg (R) graphab4py (Python)	-

Graphab and Conefor both may be used to compute "deltas" or "vars" for connectivity indices caused by the removal of each node, i.e. its importance. At the meantime, these tools are different in a few points:

- Conefor requires a preprocessing of nodes and connection files as distances between all nodes (if link exists) are mandatory to run computations, while Graphab relies on spatial data, amongst which the most important dataset is LULC raster file, i.e. preprocessed remote sensing data.
- Graphab provides users with various options of output formats, including shp, file, txt or even gpkg (which is considered to be established encoding standard for geospatial data⁷⁴), while Conefor results may be imported only as pure text files with no latitude/longitude columns as it is suggested by authors that Conefor output tables must supply other tools through joins with unique IDs of each graph node.
- Both tools are flexible to digest weighted values of nodes, patches (their area, perimeter, habitat quality, etc.) or links between nodes, according to landscape impedances (or frictions), implied by habitat suitability through which species can migrate. Although it is manageable to customise connectivity computations through these refinements, the plausibility of weighting seems to be highly dependent on sources where weight values have derived from - often from previous studies and expert-knowledge gauged from interviews, workshops, focus-groups etc.

⁷⁴ OGC 2023 Geopackage encoding standard. <https://www.ogc.org/standard/geopackage/>

Comparison of indices implemented into Conefor and Graphab

Conefor 2.2	Conefor 2.6	Graphab	Representativeness and illustrativeness	Global level	Component level	Local level	Delta level
NL – number of links		Dg – node degree	Rather not			+	
NC – number of components			Not			+	
		CC – clustering coefficient	Not			+	
H – Harary index		H – Harary index	Rather not	+	+		+
		GD - Graph Diameter	Not	+	+		+
CCP - Class coincidence probability		CCP - Class coincidence probability	Rather not	+			
LCP – landscape coincidence probability			Rather not	+			
		CCe – Closeness centrality	Not			+	
		Ec - Eccentricity	Not			+	
		Ccor – Connectivity correlation	Possibly			+	
IIC – integral index of connectivity		IIC – integral index of connectivity	Rather yes	+	+		+
F – flux			Rather not	+	+	+	
AWF – area-weighted flux		F – flux	Probably	+	+	+	
	EC – equivalent connectivity	EC – equivalent connectivity	Rather yes	+	+		+
PC – probability of connectivity		PC – probability of connectivity	Yes	+	+		+
		IF - Interaction Flux	Yes			+	
	dPC (fractions of delta Probability of Connectivity)	dPC (fractions of delta Probability of Connectivity)				+	
	dPC area	dPC area	Yes, for BC(PC) and BC(IIC) computation				
	dPC flux	dPC flux	Yes, for BC(PC) and BC(IIC) computation				
	dPC connector	dPC connector	Yes, for BC(PC) and BC(IIC) computation				
	BC (Betweenness Centrality Index)	BC (Betweenness Centrality Index)	Rather yes			+	
	BC(IIC)		Rather yes			+	
	BC(PC)		Yes			+	
		CF – current flow	Rather yes			+	

Conefor 2.2	Conefor 2.6	Graphab	Representativeness and illustrativeness	Global level	Component level	Local level	Delta level
		MSC – mean size of the components	Not	+			
		SLC – size of the largest component	Not	+			
		CCP – class coincidence probability	Not	+			
		ECS – expected cluster size	Not	+			

12 APPENDIX A4

Examples of Graphab output (connectivity indices)

Representation of IIC (integral index of connectivity) and IF (interaction flux index) outputs from Graphab (Catalonia, 1987) with a default value of patch capacity, equal to patch area (values of indices are either exaggerated or underestimated which is reflected in two distinctive groups on histograms)